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Abbreviations

WP	Work Package
LL	Living Lab

Executive summary

Although Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have proved to be a “key” to the integration of research and innovation processes in real-life settings, they still fail to provide and function according to unified and harmonized processes that are easily accessible and exploitable by academic and industry researchers. Towards this end, VITALISE aims to create the first Harmonization guidelines for Living Labs that will facilitate the access of researchers to the provided infrastructures.

This document presents the work performed for the Harmonization of the way Living Labs work for the third semester of VITALISE. Taking as a starting point the work performed for the Standard v0.1 and the Standard v.02, VITALISE conducted several Harmonization activities with consortium partners and external stakeholders in order to create the Standard v0.3 presented in this document. Standard v0.1 included the state of the art information about Living Labs in the VITALISE consortium and was the first deliverable that set up the structure of the VITALISE Standards. Standard v0.2 included activities for the production and dissemination of a wiki page that included the Standard v0.1 and work was also done towards updating the parts of the Standard that describe the data and technologies used in living labs, using a Delphi study method and collected the first set of terms for the living lab lexicon. Moreover, during the second semester, the Harmonization Board was established and a meeting with the Harmonization Body took place as well. The implemented activities for the current deliverable included the preparation of two templates for the co-creation sessions performed during the Joint Research Activities (JRAs). Also, for the current update of the Standard, it was conducted a session for updating the devices and technologies taxonomy (Delphi study), some meetings and sessions devoted to the services and procedures categorization, as well as some meetings and activities for collecting and reaching a preliminary consensus upon the terms of the living lab lexicon. In addition, during this third semester, took place the 2nd plenary meeting of the project in Helsinki, as well as the 2nd Harmonization Body meeting.

The final Section of this document presents the Standard v0.3 that will be also published in the living lab harmonization wiki page.

1 Introduction

1.1 Description of WP2

Work Package 2 (WP2), “Common Standards, Procedures and Practices” is a core WP for the VITALISE project as it handles all the work and implementation for the Harmonization procedure that is being followed. Some of the main tasks are the establishment of the harmonization procedures within the consortium and beyond, the management and organization of the Harmonization procedure events (Harmonization Body and Board meetings) and the definition and update of the Standards and Key Performance Indicators by identifying and documenting the existing Living Lab processes, and the similarities and differences among the consortium’s Living Lab partners. The Standard Versions will be updated every six months until the end of VITALISE project.

VITALISE Harmonization Body is a wider community of stakeholders consisting of Living Lab researchers and practitioners, healthcare professionals, policy makers and professionals that are interested in research performed in Living Lab infrastructures. VITALISE Harmonization Board aims to coordinate the Harmonization procedures and practices and consists of representatives from each Living Lab in the consortium, independent representatives from the Health and Wellbeing domain as well as policy makers. Representatives of other Health and Wellbeing Living Labs are also encouraged to join. This board will take decisions regarding the Standard Versions.

1.2 Purpose of the document

This document aims to present all the data collection and analysis that has been done between M12-M18 of the VITALISE project regarding the Harmonization activities. Although the deliverable is entitled “Standard Version 3”, the authors of this deliverable decided that the specific standard should be Version 0.3 as it is not yet including all the required parts to reach Version 1.0. This document does not include only the Standard Version 0.3 of the Living Labs services, methods and tools but a more elaborate version, that includes the presentation of data collection and analysis in order to result in the next Standard Version.

1.3 Document Structure

The deliverable is structured as such:

- **Section 1** (this section) provides information regarding the VITALISE project, aspects related to it, and the purpose of the document.
- **Section 2** discusses the activities that were performed during the third semester of living lab harmonization framework towards the creation of Standard v0.3.
- **Section 3** presents a summary of the changes and new additions that were done in the current version of the standard.
- **Section 4** includes all the information that will constitute the Standard Version 0.3. This Section is a coherent version of the Standard and can be read as a standalone document.
- **Section 5** provides some concluded remarks for this deliverable.

2 Activities performed towards the next standard version

During the third iteration for the improvement of Living Lab standard, the Harmonization objectives were to define a common template for the co-creation sessions performed during the JRAs, to proceed with the Delphi study as well as with the services and procedures categorization and to continue the task with terms included to the Living Lab lexicon. This section presents the performed activities towards the realisation of these objectives.

2.1 Living Lab Lexicon Creation

Following the report of March 31, 2022, the initial team working on the Living Lab Lexicon (LLL) was enriched with experts in Linguistics, Psycholinguistics and Library studies.

Table 1: The new team comprises:

Eva Kehayia, McGill University, Canada
Nancy Azevedo, CRIR, Canada
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Brendan Gillon, McGill University, Canada
Jill Boruff, Schulich Library of Physical Sciences, Life Sciences, and Engineering McGill University, Canada
Sophie Cardina, I Research Assistant Environmental Studies, McGill University, Canada

The team met monthly to prepare for the Plenary meeting in Helsinki, held in May 2022. During this plenary our goal was present to the participants the overall goal and objectives of the LLL team, to present the initial list of Living Lab terms and to begin exploring concepts and definitions for a subset of these terms. To do so, we utilized the Word Cloud method and presented to the attendees 10 terms related to Living Labs asking them to write the first three words that come to mind for each of them. Below you can see the word cloud that was generated for the term “Participatory Research”. While this is a term that represents a key concept in Living Lab methodology, given the heterogeneous backgrounds of VITALISE consortium members, there were many different words suggested and these were based on people’s experience and orientation with no clear word or group of words emerging.

What are the first 3 words or phrases that come to mind when you hear "Participatory Research" ?

Mentimeter

Figure 1: Word Cloud Results

We then searched for existing definitions of the same term: Participatory Research

- Research that includes the active involvement of those who are the subject of the research. Participatory research is usually action-oriented, where those involved in the research process collaborate to define the research project, collect and analyze the data, produce a final product and act on the results. (https://ethics.gc.ca/eng/tcps2-eptc2_2018_glossary-glossaire.html#p)

Within this definition, we searched for words that were also found in the world cloud. During this activity our initial perception regarding the need for a Living Lab Lexicon was confirmed. Indeed, it was clear that even though the VITALISE consortium members all have extensive experience in Living Lab methodology, we do not always use the same ‘language’ and the words we use may allude to different concepts. This can sometimes lead to confusion and misunderstandings and can become even more apparent when talking to different ‘players’ within the Living Lab communities that are not part of VITALISE.

We reiterate our goal to be the creation of a VITALISE Living Lab Lexicon (LLL) where Living Lab key terms can be identified, defined, and shared with the Living Lab community and beyond.

The overall vision is to facilitate and increase understanding and communication between the different ‘players’ within the Living Lab communities and all those who come in contact with Living Labs.

To date, the committee has met virtually four times. The main objectives of the two first meetings (June 1 and June 16) were, 1) to revisit the goals of the committee, and 2) to establish a process that would allow us to reach our objectives. These were further refined in the subsequent meetings (July 20 and September 1). The main tasks identified to meet the committee’s goals include to:

1. Determine which words/terms to define. How many words to include?

Creating a corpus of articles using Living lab methodology and Proceedings from ENoLL: To address the first objective, we decided to select the terms that would be included in the Living Lab Lexicon in a systematic way. To identify terms that are commonly used by those who use a Living Lab methodology, other than the original list of terms, we chose to look at the literature that has been published on this topic. To create this corpus of articles published on living labs, a Health Sciences Librarian conducted a multifile search of MEDLINE, EMBASE, and PsycInfo on the Ovid platform on August 12, 2022, using the following syntax: (Living adj1 lab*).mp. Once duplicates were removed within Ovid, 567 unique citations were imported into Rayyan, a screening platform (Ouzzani et al., 2016).

Articles were considered for inclusion in the corpus if they have been published in 2008 or later and if the study utilized a Living Lab methodology or included key words such as “living labs, co-creation, real life settings, user centered, interactive exchange, interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research, innovation, users as partners, controlled environment, participatory design” in the abstract.

The citations in Rayyan include the Title, Authors and Abstract of each article and allow one to vote as to either: 1) Include an article (if relevant), 2) Maybe Include, or 3) Exclude the article if not relevant. Of the 567 articles initially entered, we have identified 173 that will be included, 340 that are excluded, and 54 that may be included and require further checking. A second round of verification of the included articles will ensue. Once we have the final set of articles they will be download and placed on a common platform.

To the articles identified by the search above, we will add the proceedings from the ENoLL Open Living Lab Days (2013-2022).

At a second step we will compile frequency counts for the terms used in this literature and then select, from the terms that are most often observed, the ones that will be defined in the first round.

2. Consider who the target audience(s) is (are). What are their potential backgrounds?
Consider having a primary definition and potentially a secondary or tertiary definition based on context/user.

Since the onset of this process, it was clear that some words/terms can have different meanings depending on the context of use (same term/word but more than one meaning). We also observe that some groups use different words to represent the same concept (different word/term but same or very similar meaning). To represent these main groups of potential users (Academia, Industry, Government, Citizens), we decided that it is important to include words/terms from the Innovation process and the Research process. In doing so, we will strive to ensure that the definitions included in the Living Lab Lexicon will reflect the diversity of context and use by the various potential users. We will continue to work on this point in subsequent meetings.

Other than identifying the terms that will be included in the first round, in the upcoming months we will proceed with points 3 and 4 above. Once definitions for the selected terms have been created, we will proceed with a verification of the definitions through the Delphi method and discussion in focus groups and workshops.

3. Identify already existing definitions.
4. Establish a process that will result in the definitions of the selected terms.

The objectives 3 and 4 are not yet fully defined and clarified.

2.2 Activities towards definition of the Living Lab Innovation Phases

Living lab approach is a multi-staged iterative innovation process in which the focus and shape of the solution enrich and clarify the further the process proceeds (Bergvall-Kåreborn et al., 2009). As described in the protocol, Living Lab innovation process part focuses on defining in an unambiguous way, the different innovation management process phases which are or can be covered during the Living Lab activities. This is an ongoing process that begins with the study of existing models in Living Labs and other domains as among scholars and practitioners there is no clear consensus what are the stages, and how many stages there should be (Arnkil et al., 2010). Theoretical process

models e.g. from (1) new product or service development, (2) user-centered innovation and design thinking and (3) agile software development have been adopted in various forms. (Santonen et al., 2020) has provided an overview of the common phases, aims of the phase, typical methods and outcomes of these phases which is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Living lab innovation process phases, aims, activities methods and outcomes

PROCESS PHASE		KEY ACTIVITIES DURING THE PHASE	AIM OF THE PHASE	OUTCOME OF THE PHASE	
1	NEED, CHALLENGE AND OPPORTUNITY IDENTIFICATION	Discover	Identify various market demand, user needs, challenges, and competitive landscape including ecosystem conditions to get inspired and empathize with end-users.	Increase options by collecting market and user insights	Unstructured insights and market intelligence data
		Define	Analyse prior discoveries to understand the users and market niche. Select the most potential opportunities and define clear challenge(s) to be solved or vision(s) to be achieved.	Decrease options by analysing prior insights	Shared understanding of the challenges, problems and needs (a.k.a. opportunities)
2	IDEA GENERATION AND IDEA TESTING	Co-create	Co-create and generate as many high level ideas as possible with real end-users and other relevant stakeholders, which could solve the defined challenge or fulfil the vision. Use insights from prior stage as stimulants for ideation.	Increase options by ideating with end-user and other relevant stakeholders	Large quantity of high-level ideas, functionalities, features and hypothesis for value promise
		Idea selection	Test your ideas with real end-users and other relevant stakeholders and select the best ones for further	Decrease options by selecting the best ideas based on	Ranking of high-level ideas, functionalities, features and

		development. Keep your options open for different development paths.	collected feedback	hypothesis for value promise
3 CONCEPTING AND PROTOTYPING	Co-create	Co-create with end-users and other stakeholders concept(s), which describe in written or visual format what user-needs are to be satisfied and how and prototypes enables a limited end-user interaction in real or simulated environment.	Clarify idea(s) by explaining the core features of the suggested solution(s)	A set of concepts or concept alternatives grounded on verified ideas
	Proof-of-concept test and prototyping	Test your low-fidelity/tech concepts and hi-fidelity interactive prototypes with real end-users and other relevant stakeholders. Select the best one for final co-creation phase.	Make a decision, which concept(s) is going to be fully developed	Concept accepted by the end-users and other relevant stakeholders
4 DETAILED PRODUCT AND SERVICE DEVELOPMENT	Detailed development and design	Product and service development activities while collecting input from end-users and other relevant stakeholders when needed.	Develop fully functional solution	Fully (or almost fully) functional solution ready to be tested in real environment
	Small-scale real life test and piloting	Conduct usability testing and small-scale validation tests in real life or simulated environments.	Verify that everything is working before heading to large scale or final impact assessment	Small-scale exercise or pilot study to demonstrate and verify that a certain features or the general concept has practical value in real world

<p>5 VALIDATION AND IMPACT ASSESMENT</p>	<p>Impact evaluation and large-scale piloting</p>	<p>Validate the full scale and fully functional product(s) or service(s) at system level in real environment with real end-users. Regulatory approvals and clinical test when needed.</p>	<p>Validate value promise, reliability and scalability</p>	<p>Fully working product or service intend benefits, value and compatibility with in the ecosystem is confirmed.</p>
<p>6 MARKET LAUNCH AND POST-MARKET</p>	<p>Market acceptance</p>	<p>Make product or service available for potential customers via trail production and market launch activities. Establish a post market surveillance system if needed and evaluate solution market performance.</p>	<p>Collect feedback for next version revision and tracking solution performance in the market</p>	<p>Providing input for product or service improvement</p>

VITALISE Harmonization Body utilizes and builds on top of this existing models in order to adopt a new version that is accessible and appropriate for Living Labs to use and adopt.

Based on Table 2, the work of (Santonen et al., 2020), the internal discussions with VITALISE Living Lab partners and their comments provided during the interviews of Task 2.1 (reported in D2.1 Standard Version 1) a simplified version of Living Lab Innovation process utilizing commonly found terms in living lab innovation process was created and presented in the following Figure (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Simplified Living lab innovation process

The adoption of multi-disciplinary approach to describe innovation process phases has led to confusion among different stakeholders. As indicated in The Living Lab Lexicon report currently it is common that (1) some words/terms can have different meanings depending on the context of use (same term/word but more than one meaning) and (2) people are using different words to represent the same concept (different word/term but same or very similar meaning). As a result, it is argued that there is need to define more unambiguous living lab innovation process definition, which is as immune as possible to discipline derived terminology.

Living lab innovation process cannot operate in a vacuum or in a single discipline boundary. Connections must be made to other relevant innovation process related concepts. Technology

Readiness Level (TRL) approach originally developed by NASA and in 2010 adopted by European Commission to be utilized in EU-funded research and innovation projects is evidently among these concepts. Yet, using only product/technology development related scale is not fully adequate, since the degree of user engagement – the key principle of living lab process – is somewhat blurry in TRL scale. Therefore, it is suggested that in the following months, the possibilities to integrate The KTH Innovation Readiness Level™ Model’s Customer Readiness Level scale as described in D13.3 Innovation Management Report would be investigated.

It proposed that a matrix type innovation process (see Figure 3) consisting of “Customer Readiness Level” and “Technology Readiness Level” as dimensions and Living Lab service offerings in each matrix cell, would provide convenient, easy-to-understand and quantifiable process model to describe a progress of an innovation process.

Living lab innovation process and services based on KTM INNOVATION READINESS LEVEL scales		TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
		Interesting research results or initial technology idea identified	Technology concept and/or application formulated	Proof-of-concept of critical functions and/or characteristics in laboratory	Technology validation in laboratory	Technology validation in relevant environment	Technology prototype demonstration in relevant environment	Technology prototype demonstration in operational environment	Technology complete and demonstrated in actual operations	Technology complete and proven in actual operations
CUSTOMER READINESS LEVEL	9	Widespread sales that scale. Large number of active users with substantial growth.								
	8	First commercial sales and implemented sales process. Substantial number of active users.								
	7	Customers in extended testing or first test sales. Small number of active users								
	6	Benefits confirmed by first customer testing				Living lab service for this cell				
	5	Established interest and relations with customers								
	4	Confirmed problem/needs from several customers or users								
	3	First market feedback established								
	2	Identified specific needs in the market								
	1	Hypothesis of possible needs in the market								

Figure 3:Correspondence of “Customer Readiness Level” and “Technology Readiness Level” with the Living Lab R&D services

As the Innovation process model of Living Labs has not reached a stable version yet, it will not be included in the current version of the Standard.

2.3 Services and Procedures categorization

Living Labs (LLs) research methodologies gained increasing attention over the past decade in a variety of research activities. In an integrative review it was shown that, using a living lab approach fosters collaboration and participation in the development and implementation of new healthcare innovations (Zipfel et al., 2022). One of our main scopes is the development of common terms and “language” in living lab research activities and methodologies. During the current iteration, one of the scopes towards Harmonization was to proceed with the services and procedures categorization. To fulfill this aim, several harmonization activities were organized, in which a variety of internal and external experts participated to offer their views and perspective on terms, services and methods regarding the Living Labs. In particular, during this period, the 2nd Harmonization Body meeting, as well as the second plenary meeting in Helsinki took place, in which there were specific activities devoted to this topic. The realization of both meetings was of great importance, as they both shed light on defining the categories and their corresponding services. In this section, are thoroughly described the aforementioned activities, in which a variety of tools and methodologies (e.g., Miro boards, Mentimeter, semi-structured discussions etc.) was exploited, aiming to harmonize the R&D services and categories within Living Labs.

2.3.1 Workshops and meetings

2.3.1.1 2nd Harmonization Body meeting

Research objectives and questions: The aim of this workshop was to come to an initial agreement regarding the R&D services and categories, as well as define the names of each service category.

Sample group: Living Lab researchers and practitioners from the VITALISE consortium and beyond. External experts also participated to offer their knowledge and perspective within the procedure of the Harmonization of R&D service categories in the LLs.

Performed activities: The 2nd Harmonization Body meeting was carried out on April 27th, 2022, virtually via Zoom. After an update on the status and future steps concerning Harmonization activities, participants were asked to participate in two (2) tasks:

1. Create the categories to be presented on the Wiki for LLs.
2. Select the services relating to each category.

Participants were divided into four (4) separate groups using four different Zoom break-out rooms. This way, all participants had equal time and opportunity to share their perspectives.

Each group suggested a name for every category, using a Miro board consisting of 2 tables (4 Miro boards and 8 tables in total). Each table had a short description and provided instructions regarding the activity. The first table consisted of three columns: one comprised of the categories, as presented in the existing standard, another one containing the categories proposed by consortium partners, and a third one, which was empty. Participants could assign a category to services either by directly writing in the corresponding box of the third column or by attaching a virtual post-it to it. When selecting a category, participants could take into account the existing standard and the consortium suggestions or simply propose the categories they believe should be included in the LLs wiki page. Upon completing the first table, participants carried out a brief discussion to reach a consensus on the name of each category within their group.

TASK 1: Define living lab service category names

- You can use the existing names and licalab proposal as starting point which you find below. You can also propose whatever name you want.
- The aim is to create categories which will include all the LL service on the right hand side. One service can belong in multiple categories if needed.
- As a group you will have 35 minutes to define the category names.
- Write the names on the table 2 below (Name 1, Name 2, ...)

EXISTING STANDARD	LICALAB PROPOSAL	NEW SERVICE CATEGORIES
1) Networking and capacity building	1) Training	
2) Project planning and management	2) Network building	
3) Market and competitor intelligence services	3) Exploration	
4) Co-creation	4) Co-creation (and methodologies)	
5) Testing and validation	5) Real life testing	
6) Advisory services	6) Infrastructure & data management	
7) Marketing and sales support	7) Legal, financial and administrative support	
	8) Support on market uptake	

Living lab services

Figure 4: Harmonisation Activity. Task 1

The decided-upon category names were added in columns of the second table, denoting the beginning of task 2. In this task, participants were asked to separate services based on the selected categories, using Miro icons which they could drag and drop into the corresponding cell (service & category).

TASK 2: Map living lab services into correct category

- Use icon to vote, in which category each service will belong in your opinion
- You can add each service into multiple categories if you want
- You have 15 minutes to do this. Everybody will do their own voting

Table 2

Category Name 1	Name 2	Name 3	Name 4	Name 5	Name 6	Name 7	Name 8
1. Access to data							
2. Capacity building							
3. Clinical trials							
4. Co-creation session							
5. Competitor and market analysis and benchmarking							
6. Concept and proof-of-concept tests - concept feasibility study							
7. Equipment and facility rental service							
8. Expert opinion, and advisory services							
9. Foresighting (trends, weak signals and wild cards)							
10. Grant writing and funding application support service							

Figure 5: Harmonisation Activity. Task 2

The suggested category names of each group are presented in the table below (Table 1). The first table contains the standard categories, consortium suggestions, and the participants groups' suggestions proposed in the 2nd Harmonization Body meeting, in separate columns.

Table 3: Harmonization of the Categories. 2nd Harmonization Body meeting.

ID	Existing Standard		Consortium partner's Proposal	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4
1	Testing and validation		Real life testing	Assessment/or adding (testing and validation)	Testing and validation	Evaluation and validation	Testing
2			Network building	Networking and scalability			Community and network building
3	Project planning and management			Project planning and management, legal, financial and administrative support	Project planning and management		
4	Co-creation		Co-creation (and methodologies)	Co-creation	Co-creation activities	Co-creation	Co-creation
5	Network and capacity building		Training	Training and capacity building	Network and capacity building	Capacity Building	Capacity building
6	Advisory services		Legal, financial and administrative support		Consultation/Advising activities	Legal, financial and administrative support	Advisory services
7	Market and competitor intelligence	Marketing and sales support	Exploration		Support on market uptake	Market upscale support	Market exploration

	nce services					
8		Infrastructure & data management	Data flow			Infrastructu res-IT

2.3.1.2 Harmonisation Activity at Plenary meeting (Helsinki, 2022)

Research objectives and questions: The aim of this workshop was to come to a final agreement regarding the R&D services and the names of the categories relating to them.

Sample group: Living Lab researchers and practitioners from the VITALISE consortium.

Performed activities: This meeting was carried out on the 11th and the 12th of May 2022 in Helsinki. At this harmonization activity, participants were asked to vote on the name of each category, using the Mentimeter tool. The suggested service category names were based on the results of the 2nd Harmonization Body meeting. From the 2nd Harmonization Body meeting, eight (8) categories emerged, each one with a slightly different name. We presented those names and participants voted which of them could better describe the aim of each category. Participants voted names for four out of eight service categories.

In the following table we present in bold the names that have been preferred by participants in the Harmonization activity at the Plenary meeting in Helsinki.

Table 4: Categories' Harmonization Activity. Plenary meeting.

Service Category	2 nd Harmonization Body meeting-suggested names			
(ID)				
1 ¹	Assessment/or adding (testing and validation)	Testing and validation	Evaluation and validation	Testing
2	Network and scalability	Community and network building		
3	Project planning and management, legal, financial and administrative support	Project planning and management		
4	Co-creation	Co-creation activities		

1 At this category (ID:1), participants voted equally for both names in bold (12 votes for each of service category name in bold).

2.4 Co-creation templates for the JRAs

One of the Harmonization objectives in this iteration was to define a common way to perform the co-creation sessions during the execution of the three Joint Research Activities (JRAs). For this reason, several meetings among the JRA partners and JRA leaders took place, including, also, a session specifically devoted to that in the 2nd Plenary Meeting in Helsinki on May 2022. Based on the input and the suggestions made by all the involved partners, they were prepared two templates. One proposed template for describing in detail the co-creation session (research question & aim, stakeholders, structure, planned activities, guiding questions, tools & materials, setting & timeline, expected outputs) and a second one for reporting the co-creation session. Once the templates prepared, they were shared with the JRA partners to provide their comments and therefore, to reach a consensus and result in their final version. At the end of this process, the provided feedback was incorporated, and the final form of the templates was shared once again with the partners for jointly using them during the JRA co-creation sessions.

2.5 Delphi study towards a taxonomy of data and devices in Living Labs

The Delphi method was used in order to create a taxonomy that will enable researchers to search and discover in an effective and easy way the data and devices used in Living Labs. The details of the procedure and the first results are being presented in D2.3 Standard Version 2. After the 2nd round of feedback from the Delphi process, there were 2 remaining categories that did not reach the supermajority consensus in agreement and easiness to understand These categories were the “Biosignals” and “Cognitive function”.

2.5.1 Workshop Round

As there were controversial comments and results in 2nd Round feedback of the Delphi study, we decide to insert a different method in the activity in order to achieve a more effective conflict resolution. For that purpose, a workshop was organized using the mentimeter tool to gather the participants' feedback. The session's goal was to start from a general overview that serves the study's primary goal that is to support Researchers to search and discover the data and devices that Living Labs can offer. The first question was a general one aiming to go some steps back towards unveiling what researchers aim to find when starting a research study in their Living Labs.

Question 1: You are starting a research in LL that you are not familiar with and you are thinking about different ways to collect data with technical devices. What are the terms/words that you are using for searching the available devices/data collection tools for a specific purpose?

Please add your thoughts

Mentimeter

Figure 6: Word Cloud Results

The results show that the terms Living Lab researchers are using are very similar with the ones used in VITALISE data and devices taxonomy. Wearables are playing a central role in the Living Lab research, but they have a different scope than the one used in VITALISE taxonomy. “Wearables” term specifies how these devices are used while VITALISE taxonomy categories are targeting the purpose and user cases of data and devices.

Question 2: You are doing the exact same research study as before. What are the terms/words that you are using for referring to the activities that you are going to measure?

Please add your thoughts

Mentimeter

Figure 7: Word Cloud Results

As it becomes apparent from the word cloud, the terms and words that refer to mobility, movement and physical activity in general are very common. People are mostly searching based on the intended use and outcomes of the sensors.

The rest of the meeting was focused on specific categories that haven’t reached a supermajority consensus on the previous round. The participants were asked to rate with a score 0 to 5 if they agree with the proposed definition and if the definition is easy to understand.

Question 3: Vital signs with Qualifying Elements: a group of the six most important medical signs that indicate the status of the body’s vital function according to HL7 standard and additional measurement as qualifying elements

Agreement with the definition: 2.5

Definition is easy to understand: 2

The agreement rate was not satisfactory for this category. The main disagreement was the term qualifying elements that was used to describe the body height, length, weight, BMI. The participants were asked to propose a new, separate category name to include body height, length, weight, BMI. The proposal made by the majority of people was to call the new category “Body composition”.

Question 4: Do you want to split the biosignals to optical, electric, magnetic, chemical, mechanical, acoustic and thermal?

This was a new proposal that was based on the lack of agreement about Biosignals. However, all participants (100%) rejected that suggestion.

Question 5: Mobile & computer games vs Serious Games?

The supermajority of participants (81%) preferred the term Serious Games.

Question 6: Cognitive ability and mental processes: Measuring the processes involved in knowledge acquisition, reasoning, and planning as well as the cognitive control processes we need to execute tasks.

Agreement with the definition: 3.2

Definition is easy to understand: 3.4

Question 7: Extended reality - XR (VR & AR): referring to all real-and-virtual combined environments and human-machine interactions generated by computer technology and wearables

Agreement with the definition: 3.5

Definition is easy to understand: 3.2

As the score and level of agreement for these two categories was acceptably high, the design team decided to keep the categories in the current form for the next round of Delphi that followed.

2.5.2 Delphi ROUND 3

In ROUND 3, the following model presented in Table 5 was tested.

Table 5: ROUND 3 model – Main categories and definitions

LEVEL 1	LEVEL 2	LEVEL 3	Definition agreement level
Categories of devices for data monitoring and collection	Environment monitoring		Characterize and monitor the environment, establish environmental parameters and conditions. As environment we refer to the person's surroundings either indoors or outdoors.
	Human monitoring	Biometrics	Biological measurements — or physical characteristics — that can be used to identify individuals and their unique characteristics such as fingerprint scanning or voice recognition.
		Electrical biosignals	Electrical biosignals, or bioelectrical time signals, usually refers to the change in electric current produced by the sum of an electrical potential difference across a specialized tissue, organ or cell system like the nervous system.
		(Primary) Vital signs	A group of the six most important medical signs that indicate the status of the body's vital function according to HL7 standard.
		Body composition	Measurement of a person's body, used as qualifying elements for vital signs.
		Cognitive ability and mental processes	Measuring the processes involved in knowledge acquisition, reasoning, and planning as well as the cognitive control processes we need to execute tasks.
		Activity and behavioral monitoring and tracking	Monitoring physical activities and tracking their performance. Monitoring behavior and activities of daily living (ADLs).
Categories of technologies	Assistive Technology		Technologies used to increase, maintain, or improve the functional capabilities of individuals, the feeling of autonomy, safety and general wellbeing or also supporting participation.

for interventions	Extended reality - XR (VR & AR)		Referring to all real-and-virtual combined environments and human-machine interactions generated by computer technology and wearables.
	Serious games		Mobile and computer games that go beyond mere entertainment and explicitly emphasizes the added pedagogical value of fun and competition. They support the user in reaching personal goals, such as gamified interventions for health and wellbeing.

Below we present the results of the 3rd Round of eDelphi quantitative results.

Table 6: Agreement with main categories definition

Agreement with main category definitions						
	Disagree	Agree	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
1. Environmental monitoring	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	13 %	87 %
2. Biometrics	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	20 %	73 %
3. Electrical biosignals	14 %	86 %	0 %	14 %	43 %	43 %
4. Vital signs	14 %	86 %	0 %	14 %	29 %	57 %
5. Body composition	29 %	71 %	0 %	29 %	29 %	43 %
6. Cognitive ability and mental processes	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	27 %	67 %
7. Activity and behavioral monitoring and tracking	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	14 %	79 %
8. Assistive Technology	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	13 %	87 %
9. Extended reality - XR (VR & AR)	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	29 %	64 %
10. Serious games	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	40 %	53 %

Table 7: Agreement with how easy it is to understand description

Agreement with easy to understand						
	Disagree	Agree	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
1. Environmental monitoring	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	40 %	60 %
2. Biometrics	20 %	80 %	7 %	13 %	27 %	53 %
3. Electrical biosignals	40 %	60 %	13 %	27 %	33 %	27 %
4. Vital signs	21 %	79 %	7 %	14 %	43 %	36 %
5. Body composition	40 %	60 %	7 %	33 %	27 %	33 %
6. Cognitive ability and mental processes	13 %	87 %	0 %	13 %	27 %	60 %
7. Activity and behavioral monitoring and tracking	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	29 %	71 %
8. Assistive Technology	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	14 %	86 %

9. Extended reality - XR (VR & AR)	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	33 %	60 %
10. Serious games	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	40 %	53 %

As we can see in Table 6 and 7 all but one of the categories achieved strong supermajority consensus (i.e. 80% or more agree) on agreement of the category definition. The remaining body composition category reached supermajority consensus level (i.e. 70% but less than 80% agreed). Similar results can be observed regarding how easy the definition is to understand. Seven out of ten categories achieved strong supermajority level. Vital signs with 79% agreement level reached supermajority level. The remaining two categories electrical biosignals and body composition definitions were more challenging to understand. Nevertheless, both gained simple majority agreement (50% but less than 70% agreed). In the case of body composition, it was suggested that adding examples to definition would make it more understandable. The definition for electrical biosignals was claimed to be too theoretical and respectively, body composition illustrative examples were requested.

The following tables present the agreement and easiness to understand for specific items in each main category. The first column presents the main category while the second includes the subcategory.

Table 8: Agreement in the item belonging to a main category

Agreement with items belonging in the main category							
		Disagree	Agree	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
ENVMON	1. Concentration levels (air pollution levels, humidity, atmospheric pressure, air quality)	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	33 %	67 %
ENVMON	2. Technical alerts (e.g. flood, smoke)	14 %	86 %	0 %	14 %	21 %	64 %
ENVMON	3. Environmental Temperature (air or water temperature)	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	13 %	80 %
ENVMON	4. Luminosity	9 %	91 %	0 %	9 %	36 %	55 %
BIOMET	1. Face recognition	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	33 %	67 %
BIOMET	2. Voice recognition	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	27 %	73 %
EBIOSIG	1. EEG (electroencephalography)	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	21 %	71 %
EBIOSIG	2. ECG (electrocardiography)	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	21 %	79 %
EBIOSIG	3. EMG (electromyography)	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	21 %	71 %
EBIOSIG	4. GSR (galvanic skin response)	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	21 %	71 %
VITALS	1. Diastolic blood pressure	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	20 %	80 %
VITALS	2. Systolic blood pressure	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	20 %	80 %

VITALS	3. Heart rate	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	27 %	73 %
VITALS	4. Body temperature	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	27 %	73 %
VITALS	5. Respiratory rate	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	20 %	80 %
VITALS	6. Oxygen saturation	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	27 %	73 %
BODYCOMP	1. Body height	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	20 %	73 %
BODYCOMP	2. Body length	54 %	46 %	8 %	46 %	8 %	38 %
BODYCOMP	3. Body weight	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	20 %	80 %
BODYCOMP	4. Body Mass Index	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	33 %	67 %
COGNI	1. Cognitive tasks and paradigms	23 %	77 %	8 %	15 %	38 %	38 %
COGNI	2. Memory	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	21 %	79 %
COGNI	3. Processing speed	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	36 %	64 %
COGNI	4. Attention	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	21 %	79 %
ACTBEHMON	1. Walking speed	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	21 %	79 %
ACTBEHMON	2. Orientation	23 %	77 %	8 %	15 %	0 %	77 %
ACTBEHMON	3. Human body location (indoors or outdoors)	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	14 %	79 %
ACTBEHMON	4. Movement monitoring	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	29 %	71 %
ACTBEHMON	5. Human balance	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	7 %	86 %
ACTBEHMON	6. Physical activity level	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	14 %	86 %
ACTBEHMON	7. Physical performance	8 %	92 %	0 %	8 %	25 %	67 %
ACTBEHMON	8. Sleep	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	14 %	79 %
ACTBEHMON	9. Steps	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	21 %	79 %
ACTBEHMON	10. Stress level	14 %	86 %	0 %	14 %	21 %	64 %
ACTBEHMON	11. Technology usage habits and patterns	14 %	86 %	0 %	14 %	21 %	64 %
ACTBEHMON	12. Audio visual devices	50 %	50 %	0 %	50 %	17 %	33 %
ACTBEHMON	13. Fall detection	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	14 %	86 %
ACTBEHMON	14. Vo2 (maximal oxygen consumption)	43 %	57 %	14 %	29 %	29 %	29 %
ACTBEHMON	15. Blood oxygen	43 %	57 %	14 %	29 %	14 %	43 %
ACTBEHMON	16. Blood sugar level	43 %	57 %	14 %	29 %	7 %	50 %
ACTBEHMON	17. Gesture recognition and detection	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	38 %	62 %
ACTBEHMON	1. Reminders and alerts	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	33 %	67 %

ASSTECH	2. Coaching	25 %	75 %	8 %	17 %	42 %	33 %
ASSTECH	3. Training	18 %	82 %	9 %	9 %	36 %	45 %
ASSTECH	4. Walk assistance	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	29 %	71 %
ASSTECH	5. Support activities of daily living (ADLs)	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	33 %	67 %
ASSTECH	6. Natural language understanding	14 %	86 %	0 %	14 %	36 %	50 %
XR	1. Virtual reality (VR)	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	36 %	64 %
XR	2. Augmented reality (AR)	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	29 %	71 %
GAMES	1. Cognitive games	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	43 %	50 %
GAMES	2. Physical gaming - exergames	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	36 %	57 %
GAMES	3. Educational games	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	43 %	57 %

Table 9: Agreement is the item description "easy to understand"

Agreement with easiness to understand subcategories							
		Disagree	Agree	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
ENVMON	1. Concentration levels (air pollution levels, humidity, atmospheric pressure, air quality)	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	40 %	60 %
ENVMON	2. Technical alerts (e.g. flood, smoke)	14 %	86 %	0 %	14 %	29 %	57 %
ENVMON	3. Environmental Temperature (air or water temperature)	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	7 %	87 %
ENVMON	4. Luminosity	8 %	92 %	0 %	8 %	42 %	50 %
BIOMET	1. Face recognition	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	20 %	80 %
BIOMET	2. Voice recognition	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	20 %	80 %
EBIOSIG	1. EEG (electroencephalography)	14 %	86 %	0 %	14 %	50 %	36 %
EBIOSIG	2. ECG (electrocardiography)	13 %	87 %	0 %	13 %	47 %	40 %
EBIOSIG	3. EMG (electromyography)	14 %	86 %	0 %	14 %	50 %	36 %
EBIOSIG	4. GSR (galvanic skin response)	14 %	86 %	0 %	14 %	50 %	36 %

VITALS	1. Diastolic blood pressure	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	27 %	73 %
VITALS	2. Systolic blood pressure	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	27 %	73 %
VITALS	3. Heart rate	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	27 %	73 %
VITALS	4. Body temperature	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	13 %	80 %
VITALS	5. Respiratory rate	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	27 %	73 %
VITALS	6. Oxygen saturation	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	20 %	80 %
BODYCOMP	1. Body height	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	33 %	60 %
BODYCOMP	2. Body length	54 %	46 %	15 %	38 %	23 %	23 %
BODYCOMP	3. Body weight	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	27 %	73 %
BODYCOMP	4. Body Mass Index	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	33 %	60 %
COGNI	1. Cognitive tasks and paradigms	15 %	85 %	8 %	8 %	62 %	23 %
COGNI	2. Memory	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	50 %	50 %
COGNI	3. Processing speed	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	57 %	43 %
COGNI	4. Attention	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	43 %	50 %
ACTBEHMON	1. Walking speed	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	29 %	64 %
ACTBEHMON	2. Orientation	29 %	71 %	7 %	21 %	21 %	50 %
ACTBEHMON	3. Human body location (indoors or outdoors)	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	36 %	57 %
ACTBEHMON	4. Movement monitoring	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	57 %	43 %
ACTBEHMON	5. Human balance	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	36 %	57 %
ACTBEHMON	6. Physical activity level	8 %	92 %	0 %	8 %	31 %	62 %
ACTBEHMON	7. Physical performance	15 %	85 %	0 %	15 %	38 %	46 %
ACTBEHMON	8. Sleep	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	36 %	57 %
ACTBEHMON	9. Steps	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	29 %	71 %
ACTBEHMON	10. Stress level	23 %	77 %	8 %	15 %	15 %	62 %
ACTBEHMON	11. Technology usage habits and patterns	14 %	86 %	0 %	14 %	29 %	57 %
ACTBEHMON	12. Audio visual devices	50 %	50 %	25 %	25 %	17 %	33 %
ACTBEHMON	13. Fall detection	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	43 %	57 %
ACTBEHMON	14. Vo2 (maximal oxygen consumption)	31 %	69 %	15 %	15 %	23 %	46 %
ACTBEHMON	15. Blood oxygen	15 %	85 %	15 %	0 %	23 %	62 %
ACTBEHMON	16. Blood sugar level	23 %	77 %	15 %	8 %	23 %	54 %

ACTBEHMON	17. Gesture recognition and detection	15 %	85 %	0 %	15 %	23 %	62 %
ASSTECH	1. Reminders and alerts	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	40 %	60 %
ASSTECH	2. Coaching	25 %	75 %	17 %	8 %	33 %	42 %
ASSTECH	3. Training	23 %	77 %	15 %	8 %	38 %	38 %
ASSTECH	4. Walk assistance	7 %	93 %	0 %	7 %	33 %	60 %
ASSTECH	5. Support activities of daily living (ADLs)	7 %	93 %	7 %	0 %	27 %	67 %
ASSTECH	6. Natural language understanding	21 %	79 %	0 %	21 %	29 %	50 %
XR	1. Virtual reality (VR)	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	29 %	71 %
XR	2. Augmented reality (AR)	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	36 %	64 %
GAMES	1. Cognitive games	15 %	85 %	0 %	15 %	38 %	46 %
GAMES	2. Physical gaming - exergames	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	54 %	46 %
GAMES	3. Educational games	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	50 %	50 %

The following main categories achieved strong supermajority agreement for all the included items regarding belongingness and easy to understand statements: “Environmental monitoring”, “Biometrics”, “Electrical biosignals”, “Vital signs”, “Extended reality - XR (VR & AR)” and “Serious games”.

In the case of “Body composition” category, body length item was questioned. According to open comments it was unclear what is the difference between body height and length. Therefore, it is suggested that length will be removed from the category and “height – lying” (measure on a horizontal surface) will be added. Height – lying measure is often used with small children who are too wiggly to stand. Furthermore, it was suggested that circumference measurements should be added into body composition category since they indicate where the weight is located which is one of the indicators of health. Based on comments and literature review, core circumference measures include head, neck, biceps, waist, hip, chest, forearm, thigh and calf. It was also highlighted that body measures relating fat, mass, muscle, water and bone should be included. Due these modification requests it is suggested that the category would be renamed as “Body size and composition”.

In the case of “Cognitive ability and mental processes” category belongingness and easy to understand statements, strong supermajority agreement was achieved for “Memory”, “Processing speed” and “Attention” items. “Cognitive tasks and paradigms” item gained strong supermajority agreement for easy to understand while belongingness remained at supermajority level.

“Activity and behavioral monitoring and tracking” by far included the most items comparing to other categories. Strong supermajority agreement for both dimensions were achieved in “Walking speed”, “Human body location (indoors or outdoors)”, “Movement monitoring”, “Human balance”, “Physical activity level”, “Physical performance”, “Sleep”, “Steps”, “Technology usage habits and patterns”, “Fall detection” and “Gesture recognition and detection”. “Stress level” belongingness also reached strong supermajority agreement, while easy to understand agreement remained at supermajority level. Both dimensions for “Orientation” gained supermajority level. The remaining items “Blood oxygen”, “Blood sugar level”, “Audio visual devices” and “Vo2 (maximal oxygen consumption)” belongingness to this category was somewhat questioned even if all of them gained simple majority

agreement. “Vo2 (maximal oxygen consumption), “Blood oxygen”, “Blood sugar level” reached 57% agreement on belongingness. This is clearly less than in ROUND 2 model in which these items were included into “Biosignals and physiological monitoring (excluding vital signs)” category. For belongingness the prior model gained 93% agreement for Vo2 and 100% agreement for “Blood oxygen” and “Blood sugar level”. Therefore, as suggested in some comments, these items will be returned to this category and the category name would be renamed to “Electric biosignals and physiological monitoring measures”. Finally, “Audio visual devices” with 50% agreement level on belongingness and easy to understand clearly needs a new category placement. In some comment moving it to environment monitoring category was suggested.

Assistive Technology category “Reminders and alerts”, “Walk assistance” and “Support activities of daily living (ADLs)” items attained strong supermajority level for both viewpoints (belongingness and easy to understand). Strong supermajority for “Training” and “Natural language understanding” item belongingness statement was achieved, while agreement on easy understand remained at supermajority level. In the case of “Coaching” both viewpoints gained supermajority agreement.

3 Updates on the Standard

3.1 Overview of updates

Based on the VITALISE Harmonization methodology (more information can be found on D2.2), at the beginning of each standard iteration we define the objectives of the current that also needs to be in line with the ongoing activities in the project. Based on the objectives we can afterwards define which activities will be performed to realize each objective. For this Deliverable, the objectives that were defined along with the related project activities are presented in the following table.

Table 10: Objectives with the related project activities presentation.

Standard and delivery date	Objective	Related project activities
Standard Version 3 –September 2022 [M18]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updates on LL Lexicon terms (next steps) • Updates on R&D services and procedures categorization • Updates on methods and tools- preparation of co-creation templates • Updates on devices and technologies taxonomy (Delphi study) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Open Call for external researchers, the need for common language arises • First Open Call for external researchers, need for clear service definition • Co-creation sessions performed within the JRAs • Preparation for the real-life piloting phase within JRAs

Overall, the conceptual overview of the Living Lab management system remained the same. Some Sections that were not described in Standard Version 0.1 and 0.2 are included in that deliverable while some of the rests are updated. An overview of the changes for the different sections is presented below.

The following sections present the parts that were updated in Living Lab Standard for v0.2 to v0.3. The numbering of the parts is not consecutive as not all the parts are updated.

3.2 PART 1. Living Lab Lexicon

Although the Living Lab Lexicon creation procedure has evolved a lot, there are no current results on a stable version that can be reflected on the Standard Version 0.3. However, based on the preparatory discussions, we updated the LLL scope, goal and targeted audience.

3.3 PART 5. R&D Services

3.5.1 Categories

This section outlines the outcomes that have resulted from the aforementioned meetings (Section 2.2, 2nd Harmonization Body and Plenary Meeting) and included activities.

Initially, a highlighted issue was the importance of establishing a “Testing and Validation” category. All participants agreed that this category will include all the crucial information related to research activities within LLs.

“Project planning and management” seemed to be a category, which almost all participants agreed that is a vital service category within LLs. Participants underlined the importance of the existence of

a category related to the gathering of information and providing suggestions in common research challenges, such as financial support.

“Network scalability” and “Community and network building” were also categories that all participants agreed are relevant to LLs’ activities and should be include in the wiki page. Participants underlined the significance of researchers and stakeholders having a community in which they can share their concerns, discuss, and refine common procedures with other members in the community, as well as share their LL activities on a wider range.

Regarding the “co-creation” category, there was a discussion regarding its terminology (“what does co-creation really mean?”). There was a controversy between the technical and practical meaning of the term/method “co-creation” as, while the technical definition is widespread, some participants believed that in practice, the term “co-creation” may interfere in the communication between researchers. Considering that differences in co-creation methodologies and procedures greatly impact the harmonized processes in LLs, the participants strongly believed that there should be a discussion to combine said differences in a common language and concluded in the category name “co-creation” to which a variety of services and methodologies will be included.

As far as the “advisory services” category is concerned, an initial idea was to break it into different subcategories. If using the boarder definition of the term, this category aims to provide help and support researchers in many aspects of the LLs’ activities. Keeping this in mind, the category should include a wide range of services that are supported across all the procedures.

Most participants agreed that the “Network and capacity building” category, as characterized in the existing standard, would be renamed “Training/Network capacity building” or “Capacity building”.

Based on the Harmonization activities the eight (8) category names relating to different services are:

1. Testing and validation
2. Community and network building
3. Project planning and management
4. Co-creation
5. Capacity building
6. Advisory services
7. Market and sales support
8. Infrastructure and data management

3.5.2 Services

The outcomes regarding the services corresponding to the aforementioned categories derived from the 2nd Harmonisation Body meeting (task 2) are outlined below.

The outcomes reflect the majority of participants’ opinions and perspectives, as they were expressed through the workshops and discussions during the 2nd Harmonisation Body meeting.

The current services included in each category are presented in the table below.

Table 11: R&D Service Categories

Testing and validation	Community and network building	Project planning and management	Co-creation	Capacity building	Advisor y services	Market and sales support	Infrastructure and data management
access to data	innovation network orchestration	expert opinion, and advisory services	co-creation session	co-creation session	grant writing and funding application support service	access to data	access to data
concept and proof-of-concept tests – concept feasibility study			concept and proof-of-concept tests – concept feasibility study	capacity building	competitor and market analysis and benchmarking	competitor and market analysis and benchmarking	
clinical trials				expert opinion, and advisory services	expert opinion, and advisory services	expert opinion, and advisory services	
idea selection and testing			idea selection and testing	innovation network orchestration	temporary research funding	foresighting (trends, weak signals and wild cards)	
impact assessment and validation test					legal, regulation and safety standard support	marketing and sales support	

large-scale real-life testing and piloting						post-market surveillance and market acceptance testing	
prototyping test							
simulation test							
small-scale real-life testing and experimentation							
usability testing							

In total, it can be highlighted that significant similarities were noticed between the 4 groups of participants in most service categories. In particular, in the category “Testing and validation” we noticed a great agreement in the services. In addition, other services, such as “clinical trials” and “co-creation session”, were added in various categories underlying the importance of clarification of terminology or small differences in researchers’ perspective. As a general conclusion it can be noted that common services in each category, probably reflect the fact that researchers from different disciplines may have a common understanding regarding the services that correspond to each category, despite the slight differences or disagreements in the precise name of each category.

3.4 PART 7A. Methods and Tools

The outcome of the meetings and the performed activities for harmonizing the way the co-creation sessions are executed during the JRAs, was the preparation of two templates. The first one concerns all the key-points for the thorough description of the co-creation sessions that each partner will perform, and the second one includes the sections needed for reporting the co-creation sessions.

The existing tools are presented in the corresponding part of the Standard (section 4).

3.5 PART 7B. Devices and technologies

The devices and technologies taxonomy was updated based on the outcomes of the consensus meeting and Menti Workshop that was also tested during the ROUND 3 Delphi study. The outcomes of Round 3, after the analysis of the results are included in the current standard version. The current results are not validated by the panelists but are based on the analysis of the Delphi comments. The final validation will be done by the Harmonization Body and Board.

4 Standard Version 0.2

This Section will be the third (v0.3) public version of Living Labs Standard. This Standard is considered Version 0.3 as there are still sections that are not defined and have not undergone a full cycle of Harmonization. As v1.0 we are considering the first version that will contain information for all available sections. This Section is structured in such a way so that it can be separated from the rest of the deliverable and published in the VITALISE wiki page as a standalone document.

4.1 Introduction

The European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) – an international non-profit association promoting and enhancing user-driven innovation ecosystem defines living lab is “*a user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real life communities and settings*” (<https://enoll.org/about-us/>).

This wiki serves as an open space for the public review of the harmonization version and encourages open discussion about the various items that are presented. The information presented in this wiki will be updated every six months and published after approval from the governance Board and Body of the Harmonization process. In each section you can find when and by which each the version is approved (e.g., “Approved by the VITALISE H2020 Living Labs' consensus report on XX/XX/XXXX”.)

The VITALISE Harmonization process is governed by two main groups, the VITALISE Harmonization Body and the VITALISE Harmonization Board. By VITALISE Harmonization Body we refer to a wider community of stakeholders consisting of Living Lab researchers and practitioners, healthcare professionals, policy makers and professionals that are interested in research performed in Living Lab infrastructures. VITALISE Harmonization Board aims to co-ordinate the Harmonization procedures and practices and is consisted of representatives of each Living Lab in the consortium as well as independent representatives from the Health and Wellbeing domain as well as policy makers. Representatives of other Health and Wellbeing Living Labs are also encouraged to join. This board will take decisions regarding the Standard Versions.

The aim of this Living Lab standard is to guide Living Lab operators and researchers to execute, develop and maintain a harmonized framework for systematic Living Lab practices. It is not a rigid and strict representation of what Living Labs are doing but it rather be used as guidelines towards the identification of common approaches. Living Labs are structures that encourage serendipity in the way that they are working and should be handled as such. The standard versions concern mainly the LLs but they also borrow knowledge, expertise and experience from various other domains, like open science, citizen science, open innovation, innovation management, responsible research and innovation etc. on a sharing basis. Within this framework, there are several tools and methodologies exploited in LLs which could also be applied in several other research contexts.

By Establishing Living Lab management system, the Living Labs will:

1. Promote the expansion and growth of Living Lab movement beyond current actors and customers,
2. Stimulate cross-organization and transnational research collaboration,
3. Enable data sharing and comparison of the research results,
4. Increase research quality, and
5. Define a common terminology and language among researchers and practitioners.

The Figure 8 defines the conceptual overview of the living lab management system presented in this standard document.

Figure 8: The key elements and conceptual overview of the living lab management system

The following key elements will concern the Living Lab community and will be further assessed in the next Standard Version.

1. Living Lab Lexicon (LLL) – terms and definitions: LLL introduces, lists and shortly defines a comprehensive catalogue of terms associated and included in different parts of the living lab standard (i.e. 2 to 9). The LLL is grounded on Wikipedia type of user interface, where definitions including overlapping terminology, will enable quick jumping between different descriptions and to in-depth descriptions in other standard sections. LLL will help to discuss living lab related issues among the different stakeholder, who currently are using varying terminology.

2. Living Lab Business Model (LLBM): “A business model describes the rationale of how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value” (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). LLBM part is grounded on Business Model Canvas (BMC) approach (Ibid.), which consists of the following nine different elements. (1) key activities, (2) key resources, (3) partner network, (4) value proposition, (5) customer segments, (6) channels, (7) customer relationships, (8) cost structure and (9) revenue streams. The purpose of the LLBM part is to identify different attributes associated with each nine BMC element. Having a unified way to describe LLBM enables quantitative business model comparison between different living labs as well as open ups possibilities to track changes in business model strategies.

3. Research process: The part ‘Living Lab research process’ focuses on defining the key steps to execute and define a living lab research methodology. The part is comprised of (1) a common template to define research protocol, (2) ethical and data management plans, (3) participant recruitment procedures, (4) infrastructure selection procedure, (5) data collection procedures, (6) data analysis and comparison practices and (7) fair data practices for opening data. Each phase consists of aim, outcome and maturity level description. Furthermore, research process phases are interlinked with other living lab standard parts in order to identify which other items are relevant for each research process phase. Having a standard way to describe living lab research design helps

developing a unified research methodology, which enables a robust results comparison across different studies, increasing the research quality.

4. Innovation process: Living Lab innovation process part focuses on defining in an unambiguous way, the different innovation management process phases which are or can be covered during the living lab data collection phase. This part defines an iterative and agile user-centered innovation and design process and align the phases with Technology Readiness Level (TRL) concept. TRL is widely adopted concept to describe developed solution maturity level. Respectively to research process, different innovation process phases are interlinked with other Living Lab standard parts in order to identify which of the other items are relevant for each process phase.

5. R&D services: R&D services refer to a group of common R&D services, which a Living Lab can offer to its' customers during the different Living Lab R&D process phases. Each service combines one or more data collection approaches or other activities or parts of the Living Lab standard, needed to accomplish living lab R&D project as whole or part of it. Each service description defines the type of service and additional details related to service delivery such as technical and functional quality. In the long run, the aim is to define the Minimum Acceptable Service Level for each service type in order ensure service quality across the different Living Labs.

6. Living lab Research Infrastructure (RI): This part provides a classification schema and definitions for different types of Living Lab infrastructures. In regulation No 1291/2013, European Union Parliament and Council of the European Union (2013) defines RIs as "facilities, resources and services that are used by the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields". The definitions and descriptions for (1) single-sited, (2) distributed, (3) virtual and (4) mobile living lab facilities are provided.

7. Data collection approaches. Data collection approaches consist of the following three sub-parts: (1) methods and tools, (2) devices and technologies and (3) validated questionnaires and instruments. This part provides a collection of practical data collection approaches, which can be combined in multiple variations when defining a living lab project research methodology.

7A Methods and tools part identifies and describes the different types of specific research methods, tools, and practices, which can be used for data collection during a living lab project. Among these are e.g. interviews, workshops and surveys. In the future, the standard will be used for sharing the best practices and defining the appropriate ways to utilize the particular method in different living research contexts.

7B Devices and technologies defines a commonly used technological solutions to collect and analyse living lab research data. Correspondingly to 7A methods and devices, the standard will be used for sharing the best practices and defining the appropriate ways to utilize the particular technology in a research setting.

7C. Validated questionnaires and instrument consists of a numerous scientifically validated surveys, scales, interventions or similar, known to be reliable measure-certain phenomenon. The Standard will especially promote questionnaires and instruments which are multilingual and freely available. If multiple instruments are available to measure same phenomenon, standard will make recommendation to make selections.

To conclude, it is important to clarify that the above-described conceptual overview and the included key elements of the living lab management system are preliminary concepts. Therefore, the names, details and concept itself can be changed in the following versions.

4.2 Scope of this document

This is the third draft version of the Health and Wellbeing Living Labs Standard (Version 0.3). The structure and content of this document will be continuously improved and a new version will be released every 6 months. The information presented are a result of an analysis performed in the VITALISE project and more details about the analysis can be found in the Deliverables of the project. The Parts that are not presented here are the ones that have not yet undergone a full circle of Harmonization. The rest of the document presents:

- **PART 1 Living Lab Lexicon (LLL):** Collection of terms that are widely used in Living Lab performed activities
- **PART 2. Living lab business model:** The identified end users that can use the R&D services provided by Health and Wellbeing Living Labs
- **PART 5. R&D Services:** A list of R&D services provided by Health and Wellbeing Living Labs
- **PART 6. Living lab research infrastructure:** a first categorization of existing Living Lab infrastructures.
- **PART 7A. Methods and tools:** In this standard version identified methods and tools are presented as a part of R&D service descriptions
- **PART 7B. Devices and technologies:** In this standard version identified devices and technologies are presented as a part of R&D service descriptions

4.3 PART 1. Living Lab Lexicon (LLL)

It is clear that most stakeholders in Living Lab ecosystem do not always use the same 'language' and the words used may allude to different concepts. This can sometimes lead to confusion and misunderstandings and can become even more apparent when talking to different 'players' within the Living Lab communities. VITALISE is creating a Living Lab Lexicon (LLL) with the aim to create a repository where Living Lab key terms can be identified, defined, and shared with the Living Lab community and beyond. The overall vision is to facilitate and increase understanding and communication between the different 'players' within the Living Lab communities and all those who come in contact with Living Labs.

Moreover, some words/terms can have different meanings depending on the context of use (same term/word but more than one meaning). We also observe that some groups use different words to represent the same concept (different word/term but same or very similar meaning). To represent these main groups of potential users (Academia, Industry, Government, Citizens), we decided that it is important to include words/terms from the Innovation process and the Research process. In doing so, we will strive to ensure that the definitions included in the Living Lab Lexicon will reflect the diversity of context and use by the various potential users.

Below we present a first set of Living Lab terms that will be defined.

Table 12: Collected terms from LLs' activities

Collected terms from LLs' activities			
bottom up	european collaboration	integrative process	observation
co-design	experimentation	iterative feedback	open innovation ecosystem
community pilots	exploration	knowledge sharing	real life testing
constellation	feedback protection	lifecycle approach	regional collaboration
cross border living lab collaboration	governance	living lab methodology	small scale pilots
Cross-fertilization	human centered design	living lab methods and tools	stakeholders
demonstration (sessions)	human factor study	living lab research	user centered-design

end user involvement uptake inclusion	ideation	Methodology	user design research
end users			

4.4 PART 2. Living Lab Business Model (LLBM)

“A business model describes the rationale of how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value” (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). LLBM part is grounded on Business Model Canvas (BMC) approach (Ibid.), which consists of the following nine different elements. (1) key activities, (2) key resources, (3) partner network, (4) value proposition, (5) customer segments, (6) channels, (7) customer relationships, (8) cost structure and (9) revenue streams. The living lab standard defines common attributes associated with each nine BMC element.

This standard version focuses on defining customer segments in Health and Wellbeing Living Labs.

4.4.1 Customer segments in Health and Wellbeing Living Labs

End user: A person who ultimately uses or is intended to ultimately use the product, service or process. In living lab project, end user is defined as a primary study participant who voluntarily participates research after giving informed consent to be the subject of the research.

Living lab research infrastructure end user: A person or organization who purchases or uses living lab research infrastructure services to conduct a specific contract-based research and development activity (often focusing on specifically defined end user group). Living lab research infrastructure end user can also be study participant (a.k.a. end user), if living project is focusing on developing living lab services and infrastructure.

End users can be classified to non-professional and professional groups. Typical non-professional and professional end-user groups in health and wellbeing includes the following:

- **Non-professional end users:**
 - **Consumers:** Those who buy goods or services for their own use.
 - **Public health and social service clients:** Those who use public services.
- **Professional end users**
 - **Health professionals and managers:** A person providing health care treatment and advice based on formal training and experience. Also known as healthcare professional or healthcare worker.
 - **Social care workers and managers:** Those providing the practical support to help people cope with the day-to-day business of living based on formal training and experience.
 - **Policy and decisions makers:** Those responsible for making policies and decisions at local, regional, national or international level.

Business-to-Business Customer (B2B): B2B-customer is an organization that purchases living lab services from a living lab. B2B-customers can be classified to private, public, education/research, civil society organizations and networks/cluster groups as follows:

- **Private sector organizations:** (business developers and researchers)
 - Tangible equipment and device manufactures
 - Health and social service providers
 - e-health, IT system and digital technology providers
 - Wellbeing and wellness service providers
 - Pharmaceutical companies
- **Public sector organizations:**

- **Local level:** Municipals, cities and other local level public organizations providing e.g. health and social services such as primary health care.
- **Regional level:** e.g. Regional hospitals providing secondary and tertiary care, councils, parliaments, and governments as well as other administrative organizations operating at regional level.
- **National level:** Government agencies, departments or temporary pointed working groups responsible for the specific functions such as health and social services.
- **International level:** European commission departments and agencies as well as other organizations operating at international and transnational level.
- **Public funder:** Government or other European, national, regional or local public institutions who is providing public funding for a specific living lab living lab research project via call for application process.
- **Education and research organizations:**
 - **Higher education institutes:** Universities and Universities of Applied Sciences
 - **Other educational institutes** covering early childhood, primary, secondary and tertiary education
 - **Public research institutions/organizations** such as technical research centers and government laboratories.
 - **Private research organizations** such as technology and innovation centers
- **Civil society organizations:**
 - Non-governmental organizations (NGO) and nonprofit entities operating at international, national, regional or local level.
- **Networks and clusters:**
 - Company cluster organizations and company networks
 - International, national, regional and local networks

Typical approaches to define non-professional end users (a.k.a. study participants) in health and wellbeing living lab projects are presented in Table 13.

Table 13: Classification approaches of non-professional end users commonly acting as a primary study participant in a health and wellbeing living lab research project.

Age or age group			
Specific age range			
Elderly	Adults	Youth	Children

Health status			
Healthy	Patient	Rehabilitant	Recovered/Survivor

A specific disease, disorder or disability			
ADHD	Dementia	Parkinson's disease	Loneliness and Social Isolation
Autism	Down syndrome	Physical disability	Mental health
Cardiovascular disease	Idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis (IPF)	Sleep apnea/apnea	Mild cognitive impairment
Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD)	Language disability	Substance abuse (drugs, alcohol)	Multiple sclerosis
Cognitive disorder (mild, major)	Intellectual disability/ Learning difficulty/ Mental retardation	Trauma patient (e.g., a spinal cord injury)	Neurodegenerative diseases

Clients of a specific service			
Child welfare	Nursing home	Employment service	
Early childhood education	Home care		

Vulnerable groups			
Minors/Children	Single parents with minor children	Persons subjected to psychological, physical or sexual violence	Substance users (drugs, alcohol)
Disabled people	Victims of trafficking in human beings	Ethnic minorities and immigrants	Isolated people
Elderly people	Persons with serious illnesses	Homeless people	Ex-prisoners and people with criminal background
Pregnant women	Persons with mental disorders		

Living lab research infrastructure end users and B2B-customers in health and wellbeing living lab projects are presented in Table 14.

Table 14: Researchers expertise

Researcher expertise	Brief use case description
Policy Makers	Studying the impact of new service models or new collaboration models in healthcare, designing or improving policies, gathering requirements for improving health and wellbeing of citizens, co-creation of research methodologies for policy making
Experts in communication studies	Defining written, oral, visual and digital communication within a certain workplace. Evaluating (multi professional) healthcare team collaboration, communication and debriefing in various healthcare situations in simulated environments (especially in Simulation lab)
Computer/Technology Scientists	Developing systems/tools/ technologies, testing and evaluating an ICT tool, prototype and real-life testing, computer vision & AI, Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality, Cybersecurity
(Clinical, social, developmental, neuro-) Psychologists	Studying the behaviour and the mental wellbeing of participants, conducting psychometrics evaluation and real-life setting experimentation/observation/real life testing
Social workers/researchers	Investigating in accordance with the scientific methods and tools, studying the impact of new care models and/or care innovations on society, developing models for a caring and inclusive society
Researchers with clinical expertise	(Doctors, nurses, healthcare workers, specialists, physiotherapists etc.), conducting research of healthcare services and practices, research on symptomatology or epidemiology of a disease, analysis of clinical effects of research performed in the study, e.g; via real life testing
Experts in UX research and assessment	Developing the process for user experience design (UXD, UED, or XD) supporting user behavior through usability, usefulness, and desirability provided in the interaction with a product or service, addressing all aspects as perceived by users with a focus on the quality of the user experience. Studying and experimenting the best practices for UI/UX and evaluating user's experience in different situations and while using different tools
Experts in sport science	Experimenting novel training methods, and their effectiveness in various dimensions such as safety, engagement, and physical capabilities. Studying the impact of physical movements in various functions and wellbeing features
Experts in rehabilitation (physical, cognitive)	Physiology, physiotherapy, occupational health research, rehabilitation and prevention. Cognitive diseases

	assistive technology, neuromuscular rehabilitation assistive technology
Experts in performing arts	Creative health improvement (e.g. for cognitive decline) through music and dance (example: redesigning public spaces into healthy spaces: test and validate Smart methodologies, products and services through folk dance)
Business developers	Studying the product-market fit, matching a solution with a societal need, learning about the user acceptance of products and services, as well as about potential products to develop, willingness to pay, business model and ideal route to market
Pedagogues/educators	Evaluating different pedagogical approaches and their impact learning performance (especially in Simulation lab)
Experts in applied economics	Evaluating cost and performance in different healthcare processes, situations and public health
Experts in ergonomics and safety	Implementation and validation of ergonomic technologies/services to support workers and system performance, promoting ergonomics in working environments, improving both health/well-being and productivity, while avoiding occupational hazards
Citizen Scientists / users as co-researchers	User empowerment, training, design, analysis and implementation of strategies and methodologies for user engagement and for raising awareness and generating citizen participation
Biomedical researchers	Studying biochemical and physiological functions, investigating how the human body works with the aim of finding new ways to improve health. Biomedical engineering knowledge (Home hospitalization, Transitional Care, Multifunctional interaction), as well as digital biomarkers analysis (e.g., for cognitive state)
Experts in accessibility Design	Validating accessible Architectonics and escape route models with VR experiment and real-life simulations
Neuroscientists	Focusing on the brain and its impact on behaviour and cognitive functions (cognitive neuroscience, EEG-based BMI research, protocol / paradigm testing, study framework evaluation)
Innovation and design management researchers	Ecosystem and innovation management research, social network analysis. Evaluating how health and wellbeing ecosystem operates between different actors at local, regional, national and international level, including also scaling and commercialization
Experts in organizational studies	Co-creation, experimentation, organizational research, experts by experience / peer support included. Evaluation how multistakeholder collaboration and co-creation is done and how effective it is. Evaluates experimentations and experimentation culture. How users are involved into these processes

Data Scientists	Collecting, analysing and interpreting digital data, such as data analytics in healthcare and digital patient recordings (how patient information recording process is managed and utilized during the intervention by using digital tools in simulated situations)
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4.5 PART 5. R&D Services

R&D services refer to a group of common R&D services, which a Living Lab can offer to its customers during the different Living Lab R&D process phases. Each service combines one or more data collection approaches or other activities. R&D Services are parts of the Living Lab standard needed to accomplish a Living Lab R&D project as a whole or part of it. Each service description defines the type of service and additional details related to service delivery such as technical and functional quality. Living lab R&D services are classified into the following categories:

1. Testing and validation
2. Community and network building
3. Project planning and management
4. Co-creation
5. Capacity building
6. Advisory services
7. Market and sales support
8. Infrastructure and data management

It is noted that some of the services can be included in multiple categories

Depending on the nature and the scope of each service, the structure and the elements of the descriptive information vary. Below, follows a brief explanation of the R&D services structure:

Table 15: R&D services structure

Section	Description
Description	In the description field it is given a general overview of the service (e.g., definition, scope, followed processes etc.)
R&D service categories	Here it is indicated the category (or categories) to which belongs the service
Key characteristics in living lab context	In this field are highlighted the most important points/aspects of the service in a Living Lab framework
Pre-tasks	By pre-tasks we mean the several steps that are considered important to be completed before the delivery of the service
Participants' role	Participants' role refers to the particular actions/activities that are expected to be achieved by the stakeholders during the service delivery
Objectives	In this part are identified the various goals that are envisaged to be accomplished during the delivery of the service
Methods	This field refers to the methodology that stakeholders could follow for the service implementation (e.g., focus groups, training

	sessions, workshops, seminars, presentations, interviews etc.)
Tools	By tools we mean the specific instruments which could be possibly exploited during the service (e.g., questionnaires, sensors, Teams meeting, Zoom, whiteboards etc.)
Process phase	Here it is indicated the phase or stage during which the service is usually delivered

4.5.1 Access to data

Description: Referring to service, which enables customers to access or retrieve data from one or more databases consisting of relevant data, based on mutual agreements respecting ethics and GDPR, which can be used for development or testing purposes.

R&D service categories: Testing and validation, Market and sales support, Infrastructure and data management

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Usually 2 sources: already existing data, new data collected
- Data must be anonymized and encrypted
- Consent from participants have been previously acquired by the LLs when it's required by ethical and legal legislations
- Type of data: demographics/personal data, health-clinical data (e.g., cognitive, treatment changes, physical performance, care to rehabilitation), measure data, sensors' data (brain activity)
- For open data, FAIR data principles should be followed
- Ethical approval and GDPR processes when needed

Pre-tasks:

- Create a database to store data
- Define the accessibility of the database (public or limited access) and how data are collected (in an integrated way or occasional/ad hoc databases/infrastructures)
- It is, usually, needed a request that is passed to the responsible of databases

4.5.2 Intake and matching

Description: During this service, the customer's (e.g., a company, SME, a start-up, a researcher) development and testing needs are clarified for the project planning purposes. It also includes the process of mapping the customer's needs and co-designing of the strategic planning in relation to the target/purpose of the project and Living Lab capabilities to offer the particular project.

R&D service category-ies: Community & Network building, Co-creation, Advisory services

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Can be both open discussion or more focused
- Usually at the beginning of the research process
- Can be virtual/online or in person event
- Duration varies-30 minutes (very short from) to few hours or days. In most of the cases there are multiple meetings taking place/more than one contact
- Often multi-stakeholder approach: Researchers, clinicians, customers, students

Participants' role:

- Customers as co-creators

Pre-tasks:

- Discuss and understand who the customers are and what their needs are.
- Agree to a plan -usually it is made a document/contract- (set goals, explore the different services, engage the operational team
- Revise & follow-up activities with the customer

Objectives

- Make a project proposal/offer between the relevant stakeholders
- Make a project contract

Methods:

Client's needs elicitation methodology, interview/focus group/questionnaires for defining the project and collecting the needs, co-design of the strategic planning in relation to the target/purpose of the project

4.5.3 Capacity building

Description: Training, knowledge sharing and awareness raising, site visits and event arrangement. Offering training for end-users and/or practitioners to improve their skills and knowledge about Living Lab approach, co-creation, iterative development and healthcare and wellbeing market. Stimulating knowledge sharing and awareness raising by publishing professional and scientific publications and arranging events, site visits and seminars.

R&D service category-ies: Capacity building

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- The way of knowledge sharing and transfer depends on the project and on the purpose
- Use of short-term or long-term methods and courses
- Material can be both created for a purpose but also some available online

Participants' role:

- Service beneficiaries become trainees
- Living Labs can offer support for the design and facilitation of capacity building programs

Methods: Co-creation methodology, focus groups, training sessions (tech & non-tech), ethical training & legal in large scale settings, seminars, presentations, workshops, webinars, forums, websites and web-engines, events, site visits, publications, summer schools, degree program, methodological training, how to use new product

4.5.4 Clinical trials

Description: Clinical trials are experiments or observations done to evaluate the effectiveness and safety of new solution by monitoring its effects on large groups of people. Subjects are typically divided into two or more groups, one having "real treatment" by using the developed solution and the other group(s) using tried-and-true solution or not using any solution. The results are compared between the groups to evaluate the impacts.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Clinical trials are similar to impact assessment and validation test activities but follow more strict validation and approval process.

Participants' role:

- Customers as co-creators

Objectives

- To find out if new solutions are safe and effective
- Get official approval for new solution

Methods:

- Has multiple phases and classes which depend on the developed solution

4.5.5 Co-creation session

Description: Co-creation session is a facilitated group activity to find solutions for a specific problem by gathering ideas, solutions and insights from workshop participants while using variety of methods. Depending on the workshop focus, it may comprise ideation, concept development and testing. Typical duration for short workshop is from 45 minutes to 90 minutes, medium-length workshop from 90 minutes to 3 hours, and long-workshop from 3 hours to 1 day. The number of participants may vary depending on how many facilitators are available, and what kind of working methods are utilized. Typically, a workshop facilitated by a single facilitator consists of six to eight persons. Number of participants are sometimes numbered to enable them to work in pairs.

R&D service category-ies: Co-creation, Capacity building

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Fundamental features: Requires (1) facilitator(s), (2) interaction/is interactive, (3) iterative process
- Can be applied in almost all phases: e.g., ideation, concept creation/testing, prototyping, prototype testing
- Can be virtual/online or in person event
- It is a service but also a generic method
- Duration varies, but usually 2-3 hours
- Often multi-stakeholder approach: researchers, clinicians, students (e.g., paediatric project, project on language and communication). Depending on the concept all actors of the quadruple helix are contacted, number of users depends also on the stakeholders. Engagement of different stakeholders can also be achieved by running series of sessions

Participants' role:

- In the beginning of the innovation process, involve the users as the creators
- If there is a product with higher Technology Readiness Level (TRL), a ready Minimum Viable Product (MVP) is more like a focus group,
- Need finding session, focus group is more of an evaluation,

Pre-tasks: prepare session upfront with the sketches, if focus group - open questions (sent beforehand), workshop preparation template

Objectives (varies depending on researchers' interest):

- Co-creation session: Finding solutions for a specific problem with or without prototypes or mock-ups. Co-creating the actual design, sketch interfaces, make the solution tangible, Drafting (prototypes, drawing), mock-ups
- Demo-session: specifically, setup to explain about the use of a prototype or market ready product and gather (first) feedback. Often done before launching a test.

- Business model session (broader, a service?): developing and defining a business model (e.g., potential customers, sales channels, distributors, value chain, the Willingness to Pay, revenue streams etc.

Methods: Brainstorming, use simulations, group discussion / focus groups, semi-structured focus group, survey, questionnaire

Tools: Projection walls, visual mock-ups, use tangible tools for prototyping (e.g. wearables), team groups, polling (tech); questionnaires, focus groups, idea generation techniques, post-it notes, creative supplies, art supplies,

Online tools: Online system for idea generation, Teams meeting, Zoom with breakout rooms, Google meet, Miro whiteboard, Mural.co

4.5.6 Competitor and market analysis and benchmarking

Description: Quantitative and qualitative methods are used to evaluate the size of the market both, in volume and in value (also known as market studies). Customer segments, buying patterns, competition, and the economic environment are defined to identify the regulations and the barriers to entry. Defining the market by listing and describing current, future, direct and indirect competitors and analysing their competitive offering (e.g., SWOT) and user experience. Comparing offerings by measuring the performance of the developed products, services, or processes against those, which are considered to be the best in the industry. Can consist also of literature reviews to a search and evaluation of the available scientific or professional body of knowledge for the given subject or chosen topic area.

R&D service category-ies: Advisory services, Market and sales support

Participants' role: Competitors or stakeholders interested in collaborations, can be done by students or experts.

Objectives:

- Identify the “space” for innovation, not analysing only specific segments, but also looking for new opportunities
- Analyse market acceptance, support scalability and transferability potential, focus can be domestic/international/global market,
- Identify direct and/or indirect competitors, qualitative or quantitative description of the market, focus can also be in research context or innovation management practices

Methods: Desk research, acquiring the information from the experts in the field, following the market as a job profile/duty, the people working know specific segments/areas, bibliometric studies, literature reviews to a search and evaluate of the available scientific or professional body of knowledge for the given subject or chosen topic area, technology exploitation, market analysis, benchmarking, other methods combined with interview(s) with a leading reference organisation or expert(s), assessment of technologies, knowledge syntheses (systematic and scoping reviews), evaluations methods of intervention (ETMI method), workshops and sessions, measures of satisfaction of users

Tools: SWOT analysis, business model canvas, Innovation management standard (CEN/TS 16555 - covered 7 standards, after ISO 56002:2019)

4.5.7 Concept and proof-of-concept tests – concept feasibility study

Description: Concept test is a low cost and quick process in which a high-level concept is tested with real end-users via different methods such as interviews and surveys. In order to conduct a concept test, preliminary concept description must exist in written or visual format, which is then communicated to the real end-users or experts. The main aim is to collect feedback for the initial concept proposal and its possible variations. Concept test can also include a feasibility study, which also covers technical, economic, legal, operational and scheduling issues relating the proposed concept. In all, concept-testing phase verifies if a concept has market interest, while feasibility study

shows if the product or service based on concept can be developed. Collected feedback also includes improvement suggestions.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation, Co-creation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Core service in LL

Participants' role: Two main actors (projects and companies), joint work among Living Labs and interested partners/stakeholders

Process phase: After concept co-creation

Objectives:

- Verify if a concept has market or research interest,
- Testing early “prototypes” to get feedback for development, identify improvement suggestions,
- Concept feasibility test focuses on verifying if concept can be technically/economically done (preliminary assessment),
- Provide development recommendations based on user/patient/customer experience and needs, identify key measures to investigate in follow-up tests, personalized in the client need and varies case by case

Methods: Survey, demo-session, interview, Wizard of Oz

Tools: Paper prototype, visual dummies close to final (visual UI), visual VR can be used to test-multitasking (real work), long term evaluations, interviews, questionnaires

4.5.8 Equipment and facility rental service

Description: Offering equipment, labs, spaces, human resources and other facilities for rent. Some Living Labs do this based on a win-to-win agreement where money does not change hand. Also, some Living Labs require research collaboration when renting.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and Validation, Co-creation, Advisory services, Infrastructure and data management

Participants' role: In some cases, researchers can visit the LL and use the provided facilities free of charge

Objectives:

- Getting temporary human, space, technical or other facility resources,
- Enable research collaboration

Methods: Payment, research collaboration grounded on Living Lab resources

Tools: Simulation lab

4.5.9 Expert opinion, and advisory services

Description: Expert(s) who have long-standing practical and/or scientific experience in the field of enquiry provide(s) a well-founded written or oral answer for your questions, including the ethics domain/ ethics guidelines, and offer(s) advisory services on the use of specific equipment. Expert(s) are discussing ideas and problems from a different angle to respectfully challenge, test and refine ideas (e.g. as devil’s advocate looking for problems). Qualified and traceable arguments in favor of and against a specific position in an applied issue to support decision-making and development activities. Professional work is a paid service, but “consultation” can be a free of charge service. In most cases it is done by Living Lab on its own, hosting organization personnel, subcontractor.

R&D service category-ies: Project planning and management, Capacity building, Advisory services, Market and sales support

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Typically consists of one-to-one relationship between the customer and the expert, but may include opinions from multiple experts.
- Internal or external experts (local, national and international experts)
- Multidisciplinary collaboration/Pool of experts

Objectives:

- Offer advice on UX or usability studies,
- Consulting care solutions (ICT and devices), in specific/narrow fields in which Living Lab has experts (e.g., energy consumption calculations),
- Consulting on consent and ethics requirement and processes,
- Consulting technical solutions (ICT, medical and other devices, sensors, wearables, health apps, machine learning, medical engineering)
- Consulting legal issues, networking and contacting people (e.g., doctors, academia, pharmacy, healthcare professionals, policy makers, local ecosystem actors), research ideas,
- Innovation management, interventions,
- Creation of training materials and processes

Methods: One to one and group discussion, advisory board, expert identification

Tools/Online tools: ethical tools, training materials

4.5.10 Foresighting (trends, weak signals and wild cards)

Description: Foresighting is a practice of exploring expected and alternative futures. Trend is a general tendency or direction evident from past events increasing or decreasing in strength of frequency of observation. A weak signal is an indicator of a potentially emerging issue that may become significant in the future. “Wild card” is a high-impact event that seem too incredible or is considered too unlikely to happen; yet many do happen.

R&D service category-ies: Market and sales support

Objectives:

- Policy consulting,
- Create a future vision,
- Identify new opportunities and risks,

Methods: Back casting, brainstorming, user/citizen panels, workshop/session, expert panel, interview, literature review, role playing, scenarios, survey, SWOT, wild card & weak signals, science fiction/crazy ideas

4.5.11 Temporary research funding

Description: Providing funding (or an investment) for research, product and business development for small and medium-sized companies or start-ups. Typically, funding is targeted for short-term small-scale experiments or if an externally funded project has resources for this kind of activity (e.g., open calls). Also, it can be done in collaboration with local research centers, publicly funded “development companies” and networks or similar.

R&D service category-ies: Advisory services

Objectives:

- Providing funding to execute small scale Living Lab project (e.g. testing)

Methods: Offering funds within funded projects for small-scale testing or co-creation

4.5.12 Grant writing and funding application support service

Description: Offering tailored support by identifying the proper local, regional, national and international funding instruments, helping to write and manage a funding application process including finding the right partners for the project if needed. In most cases a Living Lab will become a project partner, but it can also be provided as a paid service without participation.

R&D service category-ies: Advisory services

Objectives:

- Acquiring/providing funding for “customer” to execute a Living lab project or buy Living Lab services,
- Getting project partner for a Living Lab project

4.5.13 Idea selection and testing

Description: Idea testing is a low-cost and quick process in which high-level ideas are selected (i.e. ranked) or tested with real end-users via different methods such as interviews, surveys or during the workshop. In order to conduct idea testing, different high-level ideas are pre-described in written or in visual format, and then communicated to the real end-users or experts. The main aim is to collect feedback on the already existing idea proposal. Feedback can also include improvement suggestions.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation, Co-creation

Objectives:

- Collect feedback, prioritize ideas or different alternative options,
- Lowering development risk by selecting the best/most promising idea for further development,
- Challenge the ideas from different perspectives

Methods: Co-creation workshop, interviews, focus groups, surveys, questionnaires, small group discussions, informal talks

4.5.14 Impact assessment and validation test

Description: Impact assessment is a formal, evidence-based procedure that assesses the total outcome that comes as a result of the tested activity, above and beyond what would have happened anyway. Depending on the duration and scope of the validation process impact can be evaluated on individuals, organizations and the society in the short, medium and long term. Validation is the documented act of demonstration that a product or a service will consistently lead to the expected results. Validation test ensures that the product or the service actually meets the defined requirements and demonstrates that the solution fulfils its intended use when deployed on appropriate real environment.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- The validation test is usually designed by LL
- Validation testing has to meet some minimum TRL level in order reliable test the solution impact

Objectives:

- Verify that the developed solution will consistently lead to the expected results and meet defined requirement
- Evaluate social impact
- Quantify change after solution usage

Methods: Survey, observation, pre and post measurement (short and long term), quantitative measures (e.g., physiological measures), feasibility study, usability study, interviews

Tools/online tools: Questionnaires, validated scientific scale/questionnaires, sensors, thermal cameras

4.5.15 Innovation network orchestration

Description: Establishing productive working relationship between existing and previously unconnected but complementary actor parties and helping them (companies, public health and other sector, academia, and end-user stakeholders) to work together properly and well. Handling conflicts and supporting interactions.

R&D service category-ies: Community and network building, Capacity building

Objectives:

- Establish new collaboration relationships,
- Promote Living Lab methodology and raising awareness,
- Lobbying Living Lab movement

Methods: Events, seminars, webinars, conferences, one-to-one meetings, site visits, publications (scientific and professional), memberships in local/regional/national/international associations/networks

4.5.16 Large-scale real-life testing and piloting

Description: Similar to small-scale testing but with a longer duration or larger number of test participants who are representing the real end-users of the target group. During piloting, the aim is to evaluate the full scale and near or fully functional product(s) or service(s) at the system level in real environment with real end-users to make sure that the solution is scalable. Includes often impact assessment and validation testing.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Usually, the aim of the testing defines the number of participants
- Sometimes, for large numbers the LL can hire a specialized company for support

Objectives:

- Evaluate scalability,
- Evaluate system level impact and functionality,

Methods: Testing in real-life setting with real users, longitudinal study, sensors, interview, survey, observation, ethnographic studies, diaries, qualitative/quantitative methods, pre and post measurement

4.5.17 Legal, regulation and safety standard support

Description: Providing support to navigate to the legal, regulatory and safety standard requirements and help planning to meet the requirements.

R&D service category-ies: Advisory services

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Legal design and decision-making support
- Support on signed agreements, protocol
- In some cases, external contractors for IPR, RGDP

Objectives:

- Similar to expert opinion and advisory services but focusing on legal and regulatory issues

4.5.18 Living Lab project planning and management

Description: Planning project goals, costs, schedule, list of deliverables, delivery dates and resources. Written project plan for one or multiple innovation stages is made. In the project management, planned tasks are completed by executing, monitoring, controlling, and closing the work of a project team to achieve specific goals and to meet specific success criteria at the specified time.

R&D service category-ies: Project planning and management

Objectives:

- Successful development and implementation of all project procedures,
- Supervision and quality control,
- Internal/external communication,
- Optimization of the allocated resources,
- Getting clients and funding,

Tools/Online tools: Project and planning management tools, Microsoft Teams, Microsoft Excel, email, phone, messaging application

4.5.19 Marketing and sales support

Description: Providing marketing and sales support for 1) making right contacts by giving business contacts, sales and business leads, 2) setting up and arranging meetings and events, 3) showcasing products and services in a showroom or giving online/onsite visibility in Living Lab own communication channels, 4) providing “user approved” certification, and 5) offering soft landing support to help to set up business in given Living Lab country or region.

R&D service category-ies: Market and sales support

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- It can be introductory to healthcare companies and service providers and goes up to the point of developing a BM

Objectives:

- Finding right contacts and customers for Living Lab clients,

Tools: “user approved” certification, showroom, showcasing, business meetings, interviews, events, soft landing services, sales/business leads

4.5.20 Panel management

Description: Panel is a pre-existing group of pre-screened people (e.g. patients, practitioners etc.) who have given their consent to take part in different research activities over an agreed period. Panel members have given their contact details and other profiling information, which enables fast recruitment for specific research activities as they come up.

R&D service category-ies: Community and network building, Project planning and management, Advisory services, Infrastructure and data management

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Group of patients, students but also experts, experts by experience and other staff can be used as a panel (agreement is necessary in every case)
- Having engagement procedures in place (win to win situation), social activities

Objectives:

- Enable fast participant recruitment,
- Lower the management effort (no need to fill profile information multiple times)

Method: survey, recruitment collaboration with medical professionals (e.g., in hospital ward)

Tools/Online tools: intake questionnaire, phone, open calls in social media/web, posters, email, personal invitations

4.5.21 Post-market surveillance and market acceptance testing

Description: Post-market surveillance is a “real world” test of medical innovations in patient subgroups. It is a practice of monitoring the safety of a medical innovation after it has been released on the market. Market acceptance testing focuses on collecting market feedback for the next revision development and tracking the solution performance in real competitive market conditions.

R&D service category-ies: Market and sales support

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Usually within a clinical or community research context (within the context of specific projects/the products that come out as research outcomes) and not as a standalone service.
- As normal customer feedback collection and health promotion, for continuum improvement of the tool

Objectives:

- Monitoring the safety of a medical innovation after it has been released on the market,
- Evaluate social impact,
- Identify new opportunities for business and research

Methods: Survey, observation, interviews, helpdesk logs, technical logs, complain reports, pre and post measurement (long term), market studies

Tools/online tools: questionnaires, validated scientific scale/questionnaires, sensors

4.5.22 Prototyping test

Description: Prototyping test is a low cost and quick process in which a product or service with limited functionality and interaction is tested with real end-users. An interactive prototype product or service must be available so real end-users or experts can experience it. This prototype test can be, for instance, an interactive mock-up of a web service, which interface looks like a real thing. One can navigate through different screens and see simulated content. Also, the service prototype can consist of role-playing exercise to simulate service encounters. The main aim is to collect feedback on a 'close to real' user experience as possible, but at a lower cost. Different methods such as interviews, surveys and observations can be used.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- From rapid prototyping to the MVP
- IT solutions/Physical and cognitive exercises

Objectives:

- Similar to proof-of-concept but testing higher fidelity solution,
- Identify improvement suggestions and usability test,
- Provides development recommendations based on user/patient/customer experience and needs,
- Identify key measures to investigate in follow-up tests

Methods: Survey, observation, demo-session, interview, Wizard of Oz, usability tests, role playing

Tools: Paper prototype, wireframes, interactive mockups, scaled down prototypes, visual dummies close to final (visual UI), video recording, usability questionnaires, eye tracking

4.5.23 Public procurement support services

Description: Public procurement (e.g., related to research activities) is governed by EU and national rules. Support with public contract issues and the public procurement process is given to help clients to meet the tendering criteria and/or join the tendering process. Also helping public authorities to establish market dialogue when developing the public procurement announcement. This includes Pre-Commercial Procurement and innovative procurement processes.

R&D service category-ies: Community and network building

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Pre-commercial procurement, innovative procurement, public procurement
- Project based
- Validation Software (integration) - Hardware (operational validation in real environment)
- Legal design and decision-making support

Methods: Planning process based on co-creation, pre-commercial procurement (PCP), innovative procurement

4.5.24 Simulation test

Description: Simulation is a technique that creates a situation and environment, which allows end-users to experience a representation of a real event in a risk-free environment. A predefined simulation scenario defines a particular set of conditions to resemble authentic situations in a location where a simulation experience takes place to test and to gain understanding of tested solution and related human interactions. After simulation event, facilitators and end-users re-examine the simulation experience, and various aspects of the completed simulation are discussed.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context

- Mainly for ICT solutions
- Simulation labs, smart home that simulate real-life home/specific scenarios to simulate real space

Objectives:

- Simulate real-life situations and behavior but lower cost,
- Identify improvement suggestions and usability test,
- Provide development recommendations based on user/patient/customer experience and needs,
- Identify key measures to investigate in follow-up tests

Methods: Simulation test, virtual reality (VR), usage scenarios, interview, debriefing, observation, survey, Wizard of Oz, sensors, usage logs, hospital ward, interactive patient mannequin, usage scenarios,

Tools: Audio recording, video recording

4.5.25 Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation

Description: A small-scale real-life experiment is a small-scale and short-term preliminary study conducted to evaluate feasibility of the suggested product or service and to improve it based on the testing result. Testing includes a small number of test participants who are representing the real end-users of the target group.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context

- Usually lab-based studies
- Can mostly involve qualitative feedback
- Testing quality and user satisfaction,

Objectives:

- Verify that the developed solution will work also in real-life setting,
- Evaluate usability before engaging more people in testing,

Methods: Testing in real-life setting with real users, survey, interview, survey, observation, diaries, qualitative/quantitative methods, pre and post measurement

Tools: Validated questionnaires, sensors

4.5.26 Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping

Description: Identifying groups, organizations, and people who are relevant stakeholders. Prioritizing and ranking stakeholders based on their perspectives and interest. Mapping the relationship between different stakeholders and company objectives. Deliverable(s) Written report.

R&D service category-ies: Community and network building, Project planning and management, Co-creation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context

- Within a research context / for programs and projects.
- Trying to promote a diversity-centered design

Pre-tasks: Searching and listing all the interested stakeholders/partners, contacting them, and then mapping possible contributors

Objectives:

- Identifying relevant/key/negative stakeholders,
- Identify stakeholders' interest,
- Provide information to participant recruitment

Methods: Focus group, workshop, interviews, questionnaires methodology, social network analysis, two-dimensional matrix (e.g., power, influence, interest/need, support/attitude), primary/secondary/tertiary stakeholder, the salience model

Tools: Online whiteboard (e.g., Miro), stakeholder mapping template

4.5.27 Usability testing

Description: Usability testing is a technique used to evaluate a product by testing it in order to give direct input on how real users use or would use the product or service. Usability inspection is conducted when a professional evaluator inspects a user interface and gives an expert opinion regarding the usability. This approach does not involve real user. Usability testing with real users includes real users who have no prior exposure to the product or service. In the context of Living Labs is mostly provided real user testing.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Objectives: Identify usability problems, provides development recommendations based on user/patient/customer experience and needs,

Methods: Moderated/unmoderated, remote/in-person, comparative testing, open ended explorative testing, user satisfaction, phone/video interview, usability lab testing, session recordings, observation

Tools: SUS, QUEST, feasibility assessment and other several tests, eye-tracking camera

4.6 PART 6. Living lab research infrastructure

In regulation 1291/2013, the EU Parliament and Council of the EU define Research Infrastructure (RI) as “facilities, resources and services that are used by the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields” [1]. Living lab RIs consist

- **Single-sited facility:** Unified single body of equipment at one physical location
 - Laboratory or smart home
- **Distributed facility:** Facilities, resources and services that are geographically scattered in multiple location
 - City, city district, outdoor space (e.g. nature/hiking trails)
 - sensor networks, network of homes
- **Virtual access-based facility:** Resources and services that are exclusively available via online internet-based tools.
 - Access and ability storage scientific data and repositories, tools for virtual collaboration, various computer services,
- **Mobile facility:** Facilities and resources which can be easily moved to from one place to another
 - Handheld devices and non-handheld equipment

4.7 PART 7A. Methods and tools

This section includes two templates that can be used as a tool for the designing and reporting of co-creation sessions within the LLs. In particular, the first template consists of several parts that are crucial for thoroughly describing the design and the implementation of a co-creation session and the second one includes the information considered important for reporting it.

4.7.1 Template for designing a co-creation session

CO-CREATION SESSION

JRA (Joint research activity) x

Small-case study name:

Co-creation session with: (e.g., care professionals, patients, informal carers)

General recommendations:

*The objectives and scenarios can be split up: e.g.: 1 session for care professionals & 1 session for patients/informal carers etc. We would advise you to organize separate sessions for professionals and patients/informal carers and also, to adjust and fill the template separately for each group. The set-up is quite similar, but the focus is sometimes different. It is suggested a min of 4 participants and a max of 12. If wanted, you can video tape, as a back-up (*attention to the ethics considerations – videotaping should be included into the consent form).*

Other recommendations:

- o Delay erodes quality
- o Debriefing and reflection with the team (moderator and observer) improves quality
- o Keep the research questions in mind
- o Stick as close to the data as possible (quotes, words used by participants)

RESEARCH QUESTIONS & AIM

Describe the research questions and the objectives of the co-creation session, depending on your target group and the information you want to collect.

*Some general research questions can be the same across the different regions, to be able to compare and report some results later on.

e.g.:

Session with health care professionals	Session with participants (e.g., older adults)
What is their current experience with (intervention) technology?	What experiences do the participants have from previous... (possible benefits, difficulties)?
To what extend is technology accepted by the clinicians? (attitude towards technology)	To what extend is the use of technology accepted by the participants for supporting... (benefits, challenges)?
What are the advantages and limitations of using technology during...?	What are the advantages and limitations of using technology during ...?
How do they follow up on their patients?	

*Please structure and enumerate your research questions in order to be easier to report the answers afterwards (Report template: section “Output summary & main findings”).

STAKEHOLDERS

Define all the stakeholders of your co-creation session

- The number of facilitators
- The number of observers/documenters
- The number of participants

STRUCTURE & PLANNED ACTIVITIES

Define the structure of your co-creation session(s), the activities you are planning to include (e.g., open discussions based on pre-defined questions, brainstorming, demonstration of a selected tool)

GUIDING QUESTIONS

Define the questions you are planning to ask to the participants.

*Please structure and enumerate your questions in order to be easier to report the answers afterwards (Report template: section “Output summary & main findings”)

*Some overall questions can be the same for a general part across the small-scale studies within the JRAs.

e.g.:

Session with health care professionals

Research question	Guiding questions
What is their current experience with (intervention) technology?	From your previous experience, are there any technological means that are exploited during...? Do you personally use any kind of technology for supporting...?/How do you use technology?
To what extent is technology accepted (attitude towards technology)?	Are you open to use technology? Are your patients open to use technology?
What are the advantages and limitations of using technology during...?	Are there any difficulties or challenges that you think it's possible to encounter when using technological means during...? Is there anything that you would like to be different or that could be improved?
How do they follow up on their patients?	

Session with participants (e.g., older adults)

Research question	Guiding questions
What experiences do the participants have from the use of technology so far (possible benefits, difficulties)?	Do you use any kind of technology in...?/ What are your experiences from previous (challenges, benefits)...? What kind of support you think is needed for you to use technology in...?
To what extent is the use of technology accepted by the participants for supporting... (benefits, challenges)?	Are you open and willing to use technology?/ How possible do you think it is for you to use technological means when you...?
What are the advantages and limitations of using technology during ...?	What would be the biggest return for you to use technology during...? Are there any difficulties or challenges that you think it's possible to encounter when using technological means during...?

TOOLS & MATERIAL/RESOURCES

Describe all the tools and materials you are planning to use during your co-creation session(s)
(E.g., informed consent to sign for each participant, templates, post-it, pen/pencils, blackboard etc.)

EXPECTED OUTPUTS

Define the expected outcomes of your co-creation session(s)
(e.g., current status, needs, challenges, expectations/what is needed to happen in the future)

EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRE

Here we will define the common participation questionnaires (one for the participants and one for the LL facilitators) that will be used across the study after the end of the co-creation session.

You will find a proposed questionnaire in the last pages of the report template

PLANNED DATE-TIME, SETTING & AGENDA

Define the date, time, place/setting, as well as the activities and their duration within the co-creation session. Indicate also, who will be engaged in each particular slot of the co-creation session.
Define the room set-up (e.g., board room style/round table etc.)

e.g.:

Date: Monday 30 May 2022

Time: 12:00-13:30

Place:

Time	Duration	Activity	Team
12:00	10'	Welcome and registration	all
12:10	10'	Presentation	all
12:20	5'	Split participants into tables	table
12:25	5'	Provide the templates and material	table
12:30	40'	Activities/questions - open discussion	table
13:10	15'	Each team presents briefly what was discussed	all
13:25	5'	Questionnaire	all

4.7.2 Template for reporting a co-creation session

REPORT_CO-CREATION SESSION

LL name	
WP & Small-case study name	
Facilitator(s)	
Observer(s)/documenter(s)	
Date of co-creation session	
Number of participants (total)	

Facilitator team

List the name and the email of the facilitator(s) and the observers(s)/documenter(s) involved in the session. Indicate their role in the session and their profile (e.g. psychologist, nurse, occupational therapist, physiotherapist, gerontologist etc.)

Participants' profile

Fill in each participant's profile in a different row, checking the appropriate cell.

Serial number	GENDER			Age	PROFILE (define the stakeholders you will engage)		
	Male	Female	Neutral/ Other	Year of birth	Stakeholder 1	Stakeholder 2	Stakeholder 3
1							
2							
3							
4							
5							

6							
7							
8							
9							
10							
11							
12							

Serial number	Education level								
	ISCED 0: Early childhood education	ISCED 1: Primary education	ISCED 2: Lower secondary education	ISCED 3: Upper secondary education	ISCED 4: Post-secondary non-tertiary education	ISCED 5: Short-cycle tertiary education	ISCED 6: Bachelor's or equivalent level	ISCED 7: Master's or equivalent level	ISCED 8: Doctoral or equivalent level
1									
2									
3									
4									
5									
6									
7									
8									
9									
10									
11									
12									

Serial number	Technology literacy				Previous contact with VITALISE project	
	Basic	Intermediate	Advanced	Excellent	YES	NO
1						
2						
3						

4						
5						
6						
7						
8						
9						
10						
11						
12						

ONLY FOR THE HEALTHCARE PROFESSIONALS

Serial number	How many years have you been in practice?	What area of speciality do you currently work in (i.e. neurology, musculoskeletal etc.)
1		
2		
3		
4		
5		
6		
7		
8		
9		
10		
11		
12		

Session goals

Briefly describe the objectives of the co-creation session.

List of questions & activities

List and briefly describe the questions / activities that guided the discussion for collecting value insights from the participants

List of tools and materials used

List and briefly describe the list of tools and materials used during the co-creation session.

Photos

In this section add some photos of the event (5-6). It is nice to have some photos depicting the whole event, e.g., with the tables, hands, materials etc., including also the participants, IF THEY HAVE CONSENTED, (probably blurred *ethics considerations). Also, please try to include some photos that have the VITALISE logo in the background (e.g. from a presentation, a banner).

Questionnaire output

In this Section report the output of the VITALISE participation questionnaire (ANNEX 1). This questionnaire is filled by the participants of the co-creation session. Each participant could write his/her name if he/she wants and the facilitator must report the profile category (older adult, caregiver, clinician) for whom they have provided their names an N/A for those have not.

Profile	1	2	3	4	5
	Choose an item.	Choose an item.			
	Choose an item.	Choose an item.			
	Choose an item.	Choose an item.			
	Choose an item.	Choose an item.			
	Choose an item.	Choose an item.			

Happiness of the team

This questionnaire is filled by the Living Lab (facilitators) team. The goal is to record possible problems in the procedure, the communication and the assigned work. Each Living Lab should fill only one questionnaire that depicts the average impression of the whole team.

1. Assign a score from 1-5 in each co-creation session:

Co-creation session	
How do you feel about the amount of work assigned to you in this co-creation session?	
How do you feel about the amount of work you did in this co-creation session?	
How do you feel about the quality/value of work you did in this co-creation session?	

2. What would you change? (Free text response)

3. What did you like more? (Free text response)

ANNEX 1

1. How do you feel about this co-creation session?

2. Would you like to be with us in possible next sessions? YES NO

3. What did you like most on this co-creation session?

.....

.....

.....

.....

4. What you did not like on this co-creation session?

.....

.....

.....

.....

5. Is there anything you want to propose as a possible improvement?

.....

.....

.....

.....

4.8 PART 7B. Devices and technologies

This Part presents a taxonomy for identifying and classifying the data that are collected in Living Lab environments and consequently link the devices that are used for collecting each data category. The aim of the taxonomy is to help finding the appropriate digital data collection tools for living lab research and/or expand understanding about available tools and their possibilities. Furthermore, the taxonomy aims to facilitate data collection by driving a unified representation schema of the collected datasets enabling the the cross-organizational collaboration and the accessibility of Living Labs to external stakeholders.

Table 16: Devices and technologies provided by Living Labs

			Definition
Categories of devices for data monitoring and collection	Environmental monitoring		characterize and monitor the environment, establish environmental parameters and conditions. As environment we refer to the person's surroundings either indoors or outdoors
	Human monitoring	Biometrics	biological measurements — or physical characteristics — that can be used to identify individuals and their unique characteristics such as fingerprint scanning or voice recognition
		Electrical Biosignals and physiological monitoring measures	electrical biosignals, or bioelectrical time signals, usually refers to the change in electric current produced by the sum of an electrical potential difference across a specialized

			tissue, organ or cell system like the nervous system
		(Primary) Vital signs	a group of the six most important medical signs that indicate the status of the body's vital function according to HL7 standard
		Body size and composition	measurement of a person's body, used as qualifying elements for vital signs
		Cognitive ability and mental processes	Measuring the processes involved in the acquisition of knowledge, reasoning and management of information and the brain-based skills we need to carry out any task
		Activity and behavioral monitoring	monitoring the individuals' physical activities and tracking their performance. Monitoring behavior and activities of daily living (ADLs)
Categories of technologies for interventions	Assistive Technology		technologies used to increase, maintain, or improve the functional capabilities of individuals, the feeling of autonomy, safety and general wellbeing or also supporting participation.
	Extended reality - XR (VR & AR)		allows for a two-way flow of information through an interface between the user and the technology through a simulated experience that can be similar to or completely different from the real world
	Serious Games		all the digital games that are used as interventions for health and wellbeing not including XR

Table 17: Devices and technologies subcategories

Category	Subcategory
Environment monitoring	Concentration levels (air pollution levels, humidity, atmospheric pressure, air quality)
	Technical alerts (e.g. flood, smoke)
	Environmental Temperature (air or water temperature)
	Luminosity
	Audiovisual devices
Biometrics	Face recognition
	Voice recognition
Electrical Biosignals and physiological monitoring measures	EEG (electroencephalography)
	ECG (electrocardiography)
	EMG (electromyography)
	Vo2 (maximal oxygen consumption)
	Blood oxygen
	Blood sugar level
	GSR (galvanic skin response)
(Primary) Vital signs	Diastolic blood pressure
	Systolic blood pressure
	Heart rate
	Body temperature
	Respiratory rate
	Oxygen saturation
Body size and composition	body height - lying (measure on a horizontal surface)
	body weight
	body measures (fat, mass, muscle, water and bone)
	circumference measures (head, neck, biceps, waist, hip, chest, forearm, thigh and calf)
	Body Mass Index
Cognitive ability and mental processes	cognitive tasks and paradigms
	memory
	processing speed
	attention
Activity and behavioral monitoring and tracking	walking speed
	orientation

	human body location (indoors or outdoors)
	movement monitoring
	human balance
	physical activity level
	physical performance
	sleep
	steps
	stress level
	physical performance
	technology usage habits and patterns
	fall detection
	gesture recognition and detection
Assistive Technology	reminders & alert
	coaching
	training
	walk assistance
	support activities of daily living (ADLs)
	natural language understanding
Extended reality – XR (VR & AR)	Virtual reality (VR)
	Augmented reality (AR)
Serious Games	cognitive gaming
	physical gaming - exergames
	educational games

5 Conclusion

This document presents information about the collection of data and analysis towards the creation of the Standard Version 0.3 for Living Labs in the Health and Wellbeing domain. Although the name of this deliverable is Standard version 3, the authors decided to name the Standard v0.3 as not all the parts have undergone Harmonization process yet. From the work that has been done so far, the authors concluded that there are various domains that will be benefited from the Harmonization processes and that there is need for Harmonization in various contexts (Section 4.1). The Standard Version 0.3 is an improved and updated version of 0.2 but still missing information for specific sections. The focus of this standard version was mainly on the templates for the performance of the co-creation sessions within the JRAs, the update of devices and technologies taxonomy, the services and procedures categorization and the Living Lab Lexicon task. The process will continue in an iterative way and its results will be released every 6 months. VITALISE consortium envisions to create a methodology that will continue to evolve even after the end of the project and that will be adopted by other thematic areas Living Labs (e.g., urban Living Labs) to capture the particularities of each domain and to identify the similarities across Living Lab practices.

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